

The non-observable universe

The concept of quantised space

This document contains the first 18 posts of the website <https://tn-ou.org>. It covers the posts in the period March 27 2025 till May 11 2025. Only the layout is different.

00 Introduction

The blog is about my personal search for understanding the underlying reality of our universe. It is not about an unknown reality or even a paradigm shift because as far as we know the ontological concept originates from ancient Greek philosophers some 2500 years ago.

Unfortunately in science our observable universe is known by the mutual relations between the observable and detectable phenomena. In other words, for the human observer our universe manifests itself as a reality that is completely relational.

The posts on the website will discuss the underlying mathematical structure that is responsible for the creation of relational reality. There are papers about the topic too. See Orcid: [0000-0002-2882-420X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2882-420X).

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01 Relational reality

Physics is the field of science concerned with the study of observable and detectable phenomena in the universe. The way physicists explore the observable and detectable phenomena is termed the *scientific method*. That means that physicists do *experiments* to understand the origin and mutual relations between all the phenomena.

Figure 1 shows a pair of scales to determine the relation of a shared property between the objects in both scales. We have to slide the bar with the ruler to get horizontal equilibrium and the result is a relation between both objects that can be determined with the help of the length of a and the length of b.

This is not an easy and accurate method if we have multiple different objects. But if we slide the bar exactly in the middle and weight each object separately with the help of standardised objects (e.g. grams) we can express the weight of each object with the help of these standardised measurement units in the empty scale.

In other words, the International *System of units* (SI) is a method to simplify and standardise the measurement of relations. But what we have measured with the help of these units is still a relation between both objects. That is why the use of measurement units doesn't transform the shared property of both objects into absolute properties. Because it is impossible to measure absolute properties.

Actually, we humans are also a local composition of mutual relations, like all the other phenomena in the universe. That is why our senses – measurement instruments – can only measure relations.

figure 1

If we think about the consequence that observable and detectable reality shows to be a relational reality, the question arises what kind of reality creates relational reality. Not at least because for most people it is a confusing idea that every “tangible” phenomenon inside the volume of our universe represents a relation. Moreover, mutual relations can only exist if there are differences. A difference in mass, a difference in motion, a difference in position, a difference in time, etc., etc.

Without local differences the properties of every “point” within the volume of our universe are the same. That means there is no motion, there are no boundaries, etc. However, this is not real. There are differences everywhere in the universe.

In physics every change of an observable and/or detectable relation is a change of the property “energy”. It was Albert Einstein’s famous formula $E = m c^2$ that showed that matter (m) is just a local concentration of free energy (E). Moreover, Einstein concluded that the velocity of free energy – like visible light – is not instantaneous, the velocity shows to be a universal constant, the speed of light (c).

Although every change is the change of a relation, Max Planck discovered that the change of free energy transferred by the propagation of an electromagnetic wave in vacuum space – is quantised. The quantisation of energy is expressed in Planck’s postulate $E = h f$. In other words, the quantum of energy (h) is a universal constant and f is the frequency of the electromagnetic wave (e.g visible light or gamma rays).

The quantum of energy (h) is a universal constant and its velocity in vacuum space is a universal constant too, the speed of light (c). But it is not for sure that the quantum of energy is a “solid” property because the existence of the quantum of energy only shows that the amount of change in relational reality is quantised.

This in contrast with our experience that the universe shows itself as a sequence of fluent changes and the whole sequence is termed “evolution”. This concept of our universe as a continuum was expressed by Isaac Newton in his axioms about absolute space and time.

But there is a conceptual problem. Because the linear propagation of these quantised changes of free energy (E) has a constant velocity, the speed of light (c). So it is really difficult to argue that this universal velocity of the propagation of the quantum of energy in vacuum space is just a “variable” relation.

All the energy changes in the universe are conserved (law of conservation of energy). That means that the total amount of energy in the universe is a constant. We cannot create or destroy energy thus the total amount of the quanta of energy is a universal constant. Moreover, to keep the total amount of energy conserved, our universe has to be non-local.

Every quantum of energy (h) has momentum. The Broglie relation shows that we can relate the wave length (λ) of the Planck-Einstein formula $E = h f = h c / \lambda$ to momentum (p). Because in the Broglie relation $\lambda = h / p$. And last but not least, all the changes of linear momentum in the universe are conserved (law of conservation of momentum).

Figure 2 shows Newton’s cradle. If I drop the ball at the left, the last ball at the right swings off at the moment the first ball hits the 5 adjacent balls. Newton’s cradle shows the manifestation of momentum at the macroscopic scale size. If we differentiate the radii of the metal spheres, we change the energy of each sphere and therefore the magnitude of its corresponding vector (arrows).

figure 2

In other words, linear momentum is theoretically not a singular fundamental property because it represents an amount of energy and the direction of the amount of energy (the vector). Momentum is a manifestation of the universal electric field (energy) and its corresponding magnetic field (vector field). Both fields together are termed “electromagnetic field”.

Quantum fields are part of relational reality too. Actually the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field are basic quantum fields. The Higgs field – the universal scalar field – is also a basic quantum field.

The relational properties of the basic quantum fields are described in quantum field theory. These properties are the manifestation of the local differences of these fields. Differences within the structure of each quantum field and also the interference between two or more basic quantum fields. The addition “basic” means that these fields represent relational reality at the smallest scale size. That is why the basic quantum fields are universal fields. These quantum fields exist everywhere in the universe. So we can state that the basic quantum fields together tessellate the whole volume of the universe.

Conclusion

If we think about it, it is hard to imagine that universal conservation laws (energy and momentum) and universal constants (the quantum of energy and the speed of light) are indispensable “ingredients” of a relational universe. So it is reasonable to expect that reality envelopes more than the mutual relations.

02 Non-observable reality

In 1973 I started research in the field of the mathematical nature of reality. But somehow I was not impressed by the (limited) ideas about reality at that time. So when I stumbled upon Emanuel Swedenborg’s books about the non-observable reality experienced by the human consciousness I read them all, except *De Telluribus in Mundo nostro Solari* (not available at that time).

I was really impressed by the scientific clarity of the observations of Emanuel Swedenborg, although there was no direct relation between the mathematical nature of reality and Swedenborg’s observations.

Of course there are modern publications about non-observable reality too. Like the [article](#) of Pim van Lommel et al. in The Lancet, volume 358, Issue 9298, P2039-2045, December 15, 2001 (*Near-death experience in survivors of cardiac arrest: a prospective study in the Netherlands*).

There are even [military sightings](#) of unidentified areal phenomena (UAP’s) that show the characteristics of non-matter “objects”. That means that the velocity and movements of these “crafts” don’t show the limitations of normal rest mass (matter). There are even videos made in outer space that show that these “space UAPs” are only visible at infra red frequencies.

However, there exists another meaning of non-observable reality. It is a reality that cannot be described in terms of phenomenological properties. Because a phenomenon represents a mutual relation between local differences inside the volume of our universe. So if we want to describe this non-observable (underlying) reality of the universe we have to construct concepts with the help of reasoning. Like the concept of an underlying reality that is responsible for the existence of phenomenological reality. A concept that was already described by the ancient Greek philosopher and mathematician [Parmenides of Elea](#).

In modern physics we try to understand reality with the help of experiments. Theorists are convinced that research with the help of the [scientific method](#) will result in a deep insight in the structure and dynamics of the universe and the result will be a [theory of everything](#). But the measured properties of a phenomenon are the result of the local conditions around the phenomenon. So there is quite a lot to measure and to interpret.

An exception are properties that exist everywhere in the universe. That means that these properties are part of the properties of every phenomenon in the universe. Like the universal constants (the [quantum of energy](#); the [speed of light](#)), the universal conservation laws ([energy](#) and [momentum](#)) and the universal principles ([uncertainty principle](#) and the principle of [non-locality](#)). In other words, it makes more sense to create a model with the help of the universal properties. Too much theories and corresponding data is not really helpful.

If relational reality is about the observable and detectable phenomena, the question arises what it is that underlies relational reality. Maybe the question is a bit awkward because it is for sure that the underlying reality and relational reality are actually “the same thing”. It is comparable with an iceberg that is drifting in the sea. About 10% of its volume is visible above the waves and the remaining 90% is hidden under water.

However, the universe is an enormous volume without walls.^[1] That means that the separation between both parts of reality exists “at every point” within the volume of the universe. Because it is the separation between the variable part of the structure of the volume of the universe and the invariant part of the structure. That is obvious because the volume of the universe shows to be 3D Euclidean space.

The concept is comparable with the thoughts about the nature of reality of the ancient Greek philosopher and mathematician^[2] [Parmenides](#) of Elea and his student/philosopher [Zeno of Elea](#). Unfortunately Parmenides’ original paper about nature was lost and also Zeno’s book of 40 [paradoxes](#) that explained that the paradoxes don’t exist if we use Parmenides’ concept about reality. What we know are the quotes and comments of other ancient Greek philosophers about Parmenides’ poem “On Nature” and about Zeno’s paradoxes.

My research is on the mathematical (geometrical) structure of the universe (quantised space). Because I am familiar

with philosophy I knew Parmenides as the “father” of the Western ontology. But a decade ago I discovered that Parmenides’ concept of reality is actually about discrete (quantised) space. A conceptual framework that envelopes relational reality and the underlying reality that creates relational reality.

Parmenides had another student, named [Melissus of Samos](#). His work with the title “*On Nature*” describes his own replication/interpretation of the ideas and arguments of Parmenides. Unfortunately, his work is also lost so what we know is described by other/later philosophers.

The Wikipedia page of Melissus of Samos gives information about Parmenides’ ideas. Although the Wikipedia page also shows that not everyone is familiar with the concept of a creating rest frame. That is why the wrong conclusion is made that some of Melissus’ arguments are logically flawed.

Figure 1 shows in a schematic way Parmenides’ concept. The universe as one being that doesn’t move although it has a structure with a metric (in line with Zeno’s paradox of Achilles and the tortoise). There must be a metric ($\approx \ell_c$) because without the existence of indivisible dynamical units (“atoms” in ancient Greek) there are no distinguishable differences to be found in the universe. Infinity small units create a universal uniformity.

figure 1

Parmenides’ concept of one being means that the volume of the units of the underlying structure of the universe is invariant. This in line with the experiments because the volume of a phenomenon doesn’t increase or decrease its energy and visa versa.

There is a short [YouTube video](#) of Roger Penrose mentioning the 2 most important equations in physics ($E = mc^2$ and $E = hf$). However there are 2 even more important

equations he didn’t mention in the video. The first one is about the conservation of energy ($\Delta E = 0$) and the second one about the conservation of vectors ($\Delta \mathbf{v} = 0$).

Both equations represent the phenomenological part of our universe, the universal electric field (energy) and its corresponding magnetic field (vectors). In other words every change of energy generates corresponding vectors. The smallest change of local energy is the Planck constant, the quantum of energy (h). The linear propagation of the quantum of energy is known as the constant speed of light ($\approx 300.000.000 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$).

The small cubes in figure 1 symbolise in a schematic way the units of Parmenides’ underlying creating structure and the large cube symbolise the whole universe. No matter if the size of the real universe is finite or infinite. So how do these very important basic equations and constants in physics relate to Parmenides’ concept of an underlying reality that creates phenomenological (relational) reality?

The schematic concept (figure 1) isn’t complete. Because there is no mechanism that is responsible for all the changes in the universe. And more worse, there exist a vacuum in outer space while figure 1 shows some kind of a “tangible” structure that pervades the whole universe. However that is 100% in line with the concept of Parmenides. He stated that there exists no “nothing” in the universe. All the phenomena and all the empty space are created by the same underlying reality that “fills” the whole universe.

Conclusion

Reality like we observe and detect is relational reality. Therefore it is reasonable to assume that physics is about the relations between the units of the structure of the universe (figure 1). The consequence is that the units in figure 1 must represent basic geometrical properties and also an internal mechanism that is responsible for all the continuous changes in the universe.

References:

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03 Grand theories

If there exists an underlying reality that is responsible for the emerging of relational reality, what will be the consequences? Because in our scientific culture theoretical physicists have only described relational (phenomenological) reality. Fragmented descriptions that are known as “grand theories”.

Descriptions like the Standard cosmological model (Λ CDM), Einstein’s theory of Relativity (curved space-time), the Standard model of particle physics, Quantum mechanics and its successor Quantum field theory. But every theorist agrees that the grand theories are more or less approximations of physical reality. Nevertheless these approximations of relational reality facilitate accurate calculations and are at the basis of the development of scientific and technical applications.

So if we switch from the approximations of relational reality to a more absolute description of reality – in line with Parmenides’ concept of reality – what are the consequences? Will our present conceptual framework of the grand theories still stands?

At the cosmological scale size our universe shows itself as a continuum. Not only in respect to its volume (space) but also in respect to the continuous change of all the relations (time). If we accelerate a clock we observe that its internal rate of change slows down. But an identical not accelerated clock during the same experiment doesn’t show this alteration of its rate of change. That means that the use of the term “time” for the rate of change of phenomena under different conditions is not really helpful.

Because the consequence of the experiment is that every phenomenon has its own “time”. In spite of the fact that the smallest amount of change is fixed – the quantum of energy (h) – and the linear velocity of the quantum of energy in vacuum space is fixed too, the constant speed of light (c). In other words, “time” as the universal rate of change everywhere in the universe cannot be “relative”.

Figure 1 shows Parmenides’ concept in a schematic way. The concept that underlies the model is responsible for all the known mutual relations in the universe. But it is clear that the units of the structure cannot change their shape independently from all the other units. It shows that Einstein’s “time” cannot be fundamental, it is an effect. The rate of change of local compositions of energy.

figure 1

The basic idea of the Λ CDM is the big-bang hypothesis. The hypothesis assumes that about 13,7 billions years ago *all the energy* of the universe was fitted inside a singularity, a volume less than the size of a point.

The idea originates from the extrapolation of the Hubble law, the expansion of the volume of the universe because of the increasing non-Doppler red shift of light related to the increasing distance of galaxies. But in spite of this, the size of star systems and galaxies are not influenced by the expansion of space.

It was the famous English astronomer Fred Hoyle who opposed the big-bang hypothesis and correctly argued that if space itself expands, everything in the universe will expand at the same rate. So nobody can determine an expansion. Nevertheless, according to the big-bang hypothesis in the Λ CDM the volume of space and the density of energy are supposed to be the same.

Figure 2 shows a Palladium lattice. The different colours are only meant to enhance the contrast. At atmospheric pressure and room temperature (e.g. 20 degrees Celsius) the Palladium lattice adsorbs Hydrogen atoms. Because the smaller Hydrogen atoms fit in the open space between the Palladium atoms. There is also another reason why these different types of atoms attract each other and this is because both types of atoms have the same electronegativity (Pauling scale 2.20).

If we lower the temperature of the Palladium lattice with a number of Hydrogen atoms inside – for example with the help of liquid Nitrogen – the Palladium lattice gets deformed and its surface area shows small cracks. The cause behind the cracks is simple. Lowering the temperature of the lattice decreases the amplitudes of the vibrations of all the atoms. Now the spaces in between the Palladium atoms

become too small for the Hydrogen atoms to fit inside without damaging the lattice.

figure 2

The consequence is that the increase or decrease of the energy of a phenomenon – e.g. a particle – doesn't change its volume. An energy supply or extraction changes only the velocity of its motion. This is ordinary text book stuff. In other words, energy and volume are not equal or directly related in relational physics.

One can argue that the big-bang hypothesis was the only “reasonable” idea to explain the non-Doppler red shift of the light of distant galaxies. But that is not true. There are other explanations but these hypotheses are not favourite because in quantum field theory particles are supposed to be local excitations of the basic field structure in the universe. Although Einstein's famous formula $E = m c^2$ shows that a local energy density (m) originate from the concentration of free energy (E) from vacuum space around the mass. That means that the continuous energy redistribution in our universe have to be described in terms of set theory. In line with the existence of the law of conservation of energy.

The general concept of quantum field theory is that the observable and detectable phenomena emerge from the properties of the basic quantum fields.^[1] The consequence is that the supposed energy singularity at the start of our universe enveloped the basic quantum fields too. These basic quantum fields are the universal scalar field (Higgs field), the universal topological field (electric field) and its corresponding vector field (magnetic field).

However, the gravitational field is not a basic quantum field. No matter if the field is described with the help of the theory of general relativity or with the help of Newtonian gravity. In 1920 Einstein stated that without *matter* in the universe there exist no curved spacetime.^[2] In 2010 Eric Verlinde showed that Newtonian gravity is an emergent force field too.^[3]

The structure of the basic quantum fields tessellate the volume of the universe. The consequence is that if space expands the basic quantum fields expand too. The basic quantum fields generate all the observable and detectable phenomena so in QFT Fred Hoyle's argument still stands.

At the other side of the scale size – the microcosm – the present grand theories are quantum mechanics and its successor quantum field theory, actually the Standard model of particle physics. Even physicists agree that the “tangible” reality that underlies quantum mechanics is unknown.^[4] Anyway, the description of relational reality at the smallest scale size – the Standard model – lacks a trustworthy framework. Because the Standard model uses the Planck units to create a description of relational reality that is smaller than the scale size of the observed [asymptotic freedom](#).

Max Planck derived the Planck units with the help of the Planck constant (h), the speed of light (c) and the gravitational constant (G). But gravity is an emergent force field thus the Planck units don't exist. Not at least because he couldn't show his use of the gravitational constant in relation to the unification of all the fundamental forces. The consequence is that the quark/gluon hypothesis doesn't represent physical reality. No matter that the used conceptual framework to compose the Standard model is quantum field theory.

Conclusion

If we switch from the approximations of relational reality – the grand theories – to a more absolute description of reality all the grand theories will be replaced by one conceptual framework.

References:

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- Sean Carroll (2019); “Even physicists don’t understand Quantum Mechanics” (Worse, they don’t seem to want to understand it) New York Times, 07-09-019. <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/09/07/opinion/sunday/quantum-physics.html>

04 Modelling reality

If we apply the concept of Parmenides of Elea on the universe we are actually modelling the structure of the volume of the universe. Not with the help of all the detailed descriptions of the observable and detectable phenomena, but with the properties of the dynamical volume of the universe. A model that envelopes the corresponding descriptions of the basic quantum fields.

If we try to better understand physical reality – actually constructing better models – it is common to focus on specific phenomena to get results. But there are ten thousands of papers that describe different aspects of specific phenomena. Not only in relation to the outcome and interpretation of experiments but also in relation to theoretical “exercises” to analyse (speculative) hypotheses in relation to different conceptual and mathematical approaches.

However, are the properties of specific phenomena under different conditions really useful for this type of research? Is it not reasonable to focus on properties that exist everywhere in the universe, no matter if it is part of a phenomenon or part of vacuum space? In other words, universal properties like the properties of the basic quantum fields because it is thought that these fields tessellate the volume of our universe.

Figure 1 shows in a schematic way the concept of [Parmenides](#) of Elea (≈ 500 B.C) about the reality that underlies our universe. A non-observable reality that is responsible for the emerging of relational reality. Like the underwater part of an iceberg is responsible for the part that is drifting above the waves. Parmenides argued that “nothing” cannot exist in our universe so he stated that the underlying creating reality exist also in empty space between the stars.

The paradox of Achilles and the tortoise, described by [Zeno](#) of Elea, shows that Parmenides’ underlying reality has a metric (see [the paradoxes of Zeno](#) in Wikipedia). That is obvious because Parmenides was a famous math-

ematician and an all-inclusive volume without a structure has no meaning in geometrical models of the universe. Moreover, Parmenides argued that there exist no real motion in our universe, motion is an illusion. In line with the results of all the experiments in physics that show that observable reality is strictly relational.

figure 1

The large cube in figure 1 represents the universe and the small cubes show Parmenides’ metric. Change is only possible if the units – the small cubes – have not only invariant properties but also variable properties.

It is obvious that a metric is only possible if the amount of volume of every unit is identical and invariant. That means that change is still possible if the surface area of every unit is variable. In other words, the small cubes are [topological](#) objects that deform their shape continuously under invariant volume (topological [homeomorphism](#)).

The image shows that an invariant volume cannot be deformed into a nearly 2D object (a sheet) because all the units have identical invariant and variable properties. But it also shows that one unit cannot deform its shape independently from all the other units around. All the units of the structure of the universe have to deform synchronously under influence of the invariant volumes.

Suppose the structure of our universe is static, like the large cube in figure 1. It immediately raises the question what determines the shape of each unit. I don’t mean the mutual influence of a unit in relation to its adjacent units, it is about the mechanism that is responsible for the shape of its internal (invariant) volume. This mechanism must show itself in relational reality. In other words, if every unit has an internal cubical shape forming mechanism the dominant shape in our universe will be the cube. So it is reasonable to conclude that there must be a direct relation between the

internal shape forming mechanism of every unit and the dominant shape in our universe: the sphere.

Unfortunately, we cannot fill the volume of our universe with identical spheres because packed spheres don't share their surface area. Packed spheres have only points of contact. The only solution is to imagine that all the units of the structure of the universe are deformed spheres. That means that a part of the volume of the unit has the configuration of a sphere (the [inscribed sphere](#)) and the left over part is deformed under influence of the adjacent units (the topological homeomorphism).

Now we have divided the volume of the universe into 2 parts: an amount of volume ($\approx 74\%$) that is occupied by a [lattice](#) of spheres and an amount of volume ($\approx 26\%$) that represents the deformed parts of each unit. The first volume ($\approx 74\%$) must be a universal [scalar field](#) (the Higgs field) and the second volume ($\approx 26\%$) is a universal topological field (the electric field).

If all the units deform in a synchronised way under influence of the identical spherical shape forming mechanism of each unit, the continuous deformation is quantised. Because 1 unit cannot interrupt the synchronised deformation of all the other units. The deformation has a duration thus the linear propagation of 1 fixed amount of topological deformation (h) in vacuum space has a fixed velocity (c).

Conclusion

Parmenides' concept of an underlying creating reality explains the existence of the 2 universal conservation laws (energy and momentum), the 2 universal constants (h and c), the mechanism behind change/motion (the spherical shape forming mechanism) and the principle of non-locality. An indication that Parmenides' model is trustworthy. More details can be find at Zenodo.org or in the references [\[1\]\[2\]\[3\]](#)

References:

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05 Supernatural reality

Parmenides' concept of an underlying reality that creates relational reality seems to be weird. It is difficult to imagine that our experiences in daily live are not real in itself. Because if our experiences are some kind of an illusion why does this illusion seems to be logical and is governed by cause and effect and even universal constants and conservation laws. So if daily reality is an illusion, what about "supernatural" reality?

The image below shows a display of LED's in a square arrangement (grid). The LED display shows text because all the LED's can be individually put on and off. We can change the text with something like "TOM's BAR" and even programming the display in such a way that the text moves from right to the left.

Nobody who watches the scroll of TOM's BAR will conclude that these characters are independent beings in motion. Even if we watch a video on a high resolution LCD monitor we know that the video isn't reality itself. It is a 2D reproduction of observable reality.

The square grid of the LED's in the image above show some resemblance with the 2D face of the schematic image of Parmenides' concept of reality (figure 1). In other words, if we build a 3D transparent LED display we can imitate relational reality if we program the lattice with moving shapes in every direction.

Now the most significant issue is not the imitation itself, it is the fact that motion is not what we experience in daily live. If I walk in the open air I don't experience that the rest frame of the universe is propagating my body from unit to unit. I have the impression that I am "pushing" the air around me, like a ship is pushing the water aside with its stem. In other words, I am a unity and the air around me is not part of it. Actually the text books have told me that the air around is just a gas mixture, composed by a large number of fast free moving molecules.

Our universe shows itself as a continuum and the consequence is evolution, although the concept of evolution

originates from phenomenological reality. But from the mathematical point of view evolution is just a sequence of synchronised transformations of (and by) the units of the structure of our universe.

figure 1

So if we roll back the evolution of our universe there was a period there was no matter. That means that the whole universe was filled with electromagnetic amplitudes around the scalars of a flat Higgs field. Now what does that mean.

The deformable part of our universe – in QFT termed the universal electric field – is a topological field under invariant volume. Thus a unit can deform its shape but not increase or decrease its volume. The “power” to create this transformation is the internal spherical shape forming mechanism. In short: scalar mechanism. The origin of this mechanism is that every unit of the structure of the universe is actually a deformed scalar. In other words, its internal scalar mechanism is forced continuously to regain the shape of a sphere because there exists no stability (symmetry) inside the structure of the universe. We can imagine that all the “original” scalars (spheres) are pushed together so they are forced to deform till there is no empty space left between the spheres.^[1]

figure 2

To regain the shape of a sphere a unit has to reconfigure its deformed area and these area are at the points of contact between the scalar of the unit and the scalars of the adjacent units. Figure 2 shows in a schematic way 3 units

and each unit represents a different point of view. Unit I shows the inscribed sphere (scalar) and the deformed part of the unit around. Unit II shows the imaginary vectors within the scalar because of the “power” of the scalar mechanism and its limitation by the points of contact with the adjacent scalars. Unit III is a schematic cross section of the scalar mechanism of the unit.

The consequence of the points of contact between the scalars is that the fixed topological deformation of the unit – the Planck constant – is distributed over 1 or more points of contact. Thus the Planck constant – the electric field – creates corresponding vectors that are mediated by the scalars of the flat Higgs field.^[2] These corresponding vectors are termed magnetic field in QFT. Both fields together are termed electromagnetic field.

Without matter in the universe there are only the continuous changing amplitudes of the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field. The amount of “power” of each unit is half the Planck constant ($\frac{1}{2} h$). Because the whole topological deformation of a unit is caused by an input deformation from around and an output deformation to one or more units around. So this is the origin of the 2 universal conservation laws (energy and momentum).

If matter is created the lattice of the flat Higgs field is disrupted by decreased scalars. A decreased scalar cannot mediate the vectors of the magnetic field. Nevertheless the “power” of the universal electric field is conserved. So now we get the awkward situation that the direct correspondence between the amplitudes of the universal electric field and the generated magnitudes of the vectors of the magnetic field is partly changed into an indirect correspondence. What does that mean?

The velocity of the propagation of the quanta of energy between the units is the speed of light ($c \approx 300.000.000 \text{ ms}^{-1}$). But the velocity of a vector is instantaneous, because a vector doesn't propagate energy. A vector influence the direction of the propagation of energy by the universal electric field. The progression of a vector within the points of contact of the scalars of the Higgs field is only determined by the existence of opposite vectors and "co-moving" vectors.

If there is no matter in the universe every quantum of energy generates corresponding vectors and these corresponding vectors determine the distribution of the direction of the next fixed topological deformation (the Planck con-

stant) of the involved units. In other words “there is a place for every egg in the egg carton” if there are no decreased scalars in the universe.

If there are decreased scalars the symmetry between the universal electric field and the corresponding magnetic field is broken. The asymmetry shows itself as a local deficit of corresponding vectors with the right magnitudes and somewhere else as a local surplus of vectors with the right magnitudes. Of course the asymmetry will restore the balance with the help of an indirect correspondence. It means that local configurations of energy – like human bodies – get a surplus of motion. But that is not how we interpret this surplus of motion. The surplus is sometimes interpreted as “free will” and seems part of our [consciousness](#).^[3]

Local concentrations of energy are not limited to matter. Because of the synchronisation and conservation of all the quanta transfer in the universe^[4] local concentrations of energy can be “tangible” too because of the continuous “push” by scalar mechanism of every unit.

More than 13,7 billion years ago there was a surplus of energy everywhere in vacuum space because there were no large scale structures of matter like full grown [galaxies](#). But the surplus of energy – energy density – everywhere in vacuum space caused the creation of [primordial black holes](#). Actually enormous “particles” that envelope decreased scalars of the Higgs field. See the schematic diagram in figure 3. The red horizontal line is the surplus of surface area (energy density) in the universe.

figure 3

The consequence was that at a certain moment the energy density of vacuum space was no longer sufficient to create new black holes. Thus the concentration of energy continued with creating particles. The James Webb Space Telescope observations show that in the early universe the mass of the black hole in the centre of a galaxy was dominant. But 13,7 billion years later the mass of the primordial black hole in the centre of a galaxy is 0,1% or less.

In other words, there are local concentrations of energy in vacuum space and these phenomena are not abandoned from local vectors with a surplus of higher magnitudes. So there exists “live” without matter (rest mass).

Conclusion

[Supernatural](#) reality is part of the dynamics of relational reality but it is not part of the theories in theoretical physics. Actually, academic physics seems to be a bit boring in relation to the intriguing world of supernatural reality. But supernatural is complicated too. So this will not be the only post about the subject.

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06 Vector space

In quantum mechanics vector space is directly related with multidimensional Hilbert space. Nevertheless in 3D quantised space vectors have a different meaning. Vectors are mediated by the scalars of the Higgs field if the involved scalars have exactly the same magnitude (radius).

The dynamical part of the structure of the universe is the universal electric field and its corresponding field, the magnetic field. Both fields together are termed *electromagnetic field* and represent basic quantum fields at the smallest scale size of reality. The Higgs field is a basic quantum field too but this is the universal scalar field. A scalar can only change its radius so scalars don’t influence “dynamical reality” in a direct way.^[1]

If we reverse the direction of the evolution of the universe we will arrive at a moment that there was no matter in the universe. That means that the whole scalar field (Higgs field) was perfectly flat. In physics a volume without rest mass carrying particles – actually decreased scalars – is termed “vacuum space”. The consequence is that the uni-

versal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field represented all the dynamics in the primordial universe.

figure 1

Without matter in the universe every change of the shape of a unit in quantised space creates a number of vectors that are mediated by the scalars of the Higgs field.^[2] The magnitude of these vectors together correspond with the total amount of topological deformation of the unit. In other words, the structure of the universe – quantised space – is responsible for the emergence of different basic quantum fields. So we can interpret each unit of quantised space as the boundary of 3 types of properties that “create” these 3 basic quantum fields. These basic properties are geometrical properties and that is why it is reasonable to describe these properties in terms of geometry (scalars, vectors and topological deformation of invariant volumes).

figure 2

In our present universe there is matter and that means there are decreased scalars too, inclusive the emergence of the force of gravity. Without mass in the universe every fixed amount of change ($1 h$) generates corresponding vectors of the magnetic field. But a decreased scalar creates also vectors in the lattice of scalars in vacuum space around. Moreover, every decreased scalar blocks vectors. Because vectors are mediated by the points of contact between the scalars in vacuum space. Figure 1 shows the lattice and figure 2 the created vectors by the points of contact.

If a scalar decreases its radius its resistance against deformation by a huge amount of units around increases. But the consequence is that the scalars of the 12 adjacent units

have no longer a symmetrical distribution of their own resistance against deformation (figure 2). Because one of the 12 points of contact is vanished by the unit with the decreased scalar. The resistance against deformation of a unit in a flat scalar lattice is $r = 1,0$ (red line). That means that all the scalars around the unit with decreased scalar get vectorised and all the vectors point towards the unit with decreased scalar (see figure 4). Unfortunately the consequence is a vector problem.

figure 3

In the primordial universe the change of the shape of every unit had corresponding vectors because all the dynamics was restricted to the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field. It means that for every local fixed amount of deformation (h) there was a local fixed amount of vectors and the sum of the magnitudes of the vectors corresponded to the amount of energy. It is like the correspondence performs as a kind of “shortcut” (direct influence). The consequence is that all the energy in the universe is conserved and all the corresponding vectors too. But it is obvious that the unit with the decreased scalar cannot mediate vectors.

figure 4

The universal electric field propagates the fixed amount of topological deformation (h) with the constant speed of light. But vectors don't propagate energy. Vectors determine the direction of the topological deformation because vectors are mediated by the scalars of the flat Higgs field. In other words, vectors act instantaneously. That is in line with the principle of non-locality. Because non-locality means that everything in the universe influences everything at exactly the same moment.

The total magnitude of all the red vectors in the schematic figure 4 will be equal to the magnitude of the vectors through the vanished 12 points of contact of the unit with the decreased scalar (red). However, the topological deformation of the unit in the centre is higher than the scalar vectors of the units around. In other words there seems to be missing vectors (magnitude) although there is the universal conservation of the magnitude of vectors.

However every unit changes its shape with a fixed amount of topological deformation. The consequence is that there is a surplus of vector magnitude that will be redirected and will effect the direction of the topological deformation of units in an indirect way.

A black hole has a large volume and all the scalars inside a black hole are decreased scalars. In other words the effect of a surplus of vector magnitudes must be "visible" in vacuum space around the black hole. Although it is difficult to determine how the effect will manifest itself.

Conclusion

The emergence of matter in the universe has drastically changed the direct correspondence between the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field. Moreover, it hints to the existence of "hidden physics" that doesn't rhyme with the limited concepts of phenomenological physics (the mechanical world view).

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07 Determinism & synchronisation

The idea that reality is deterministic is not really popular. We like to think that we have free will because it suggests that our personal achievements are deserved. YouTube is full of videos that tell the listeners that if they want they can change their lives to become healthier and happier too. Remote viewers and channellers describe a multidimensional universe of experiences that can be navigated with the help of our free will.^[1] However, experiences are not always the best advisers to understand reality.

There are 2 universal conservation laws. Both universal laws describe the continuous changes within the volume of our universe. So it is about the dynamics – relational reality – and the consequence is that the 2 laws describe the conservation of all the changes within and between the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field. The universal electric field is a topological field, responsible for e.g. wave phenomena, probability^[2] and the quantum of energy (QM). The magnetic field is a vector field, generated by the changes of the universal electric field and mediated by all the identical scalars of the Higgs field (in vacuum space all the scalars have the same magnitude).

The total amount of changes at exactly the same moment of the universal electric field is conserved, in line with the principle of non-locality. But we cannot conclude that it proves that our universe is deterministic because determinism is not only about the sum of all the changes, it is about the relations between all the changes too. However, all the changes of the universal electric field are quantised – the Planck constant (h) – and the propagation of the changes within the structure of quantised space is a constant too, the speed of light (c).

figure 1

The vectors of the magnetic field are generated by the changes of the universal electric field^[3] so there is no “escape”: our universe is 100% deterministic. No matter all the experiences that suggest that we have a free will.

The previous post described the asymmetry between the changes within the universal electric field and the generated corresponding vectors of the magnetic field under influence of matter. So how do we have to interpret the asymmetry and how does it affect relational reality?

Energy is the creation of the internal scalar mechanism of every unit of quantised space. Because the unit of quantised space is a deformed scalar. It manifests itself by the fluent changes of the surface area of the units. In other words, the quantum of energy is surface area. Like the formula about the equivalence of matter (m) and free energy (E) shows: $E = m c^2$.

Figure 1 shows the increase of surface area of 1 quantum of energy and the generated corresponding increase of the magnitude of the involved vectors. Of course there exist already local vectors thus the increase of topological deformation ($1 h$) add or subtract the magnitude of the vectors to or from the existing vectors. In between the period of $5,99 \times 10^{-23}$ second – the constant of quantum time ($1 t_q$) – there is no change in the direction of the ongoing topological deformation of the unit. Because every unit has an invariant equal volume and all the volumes tessellate the volume of the universe. But the magnitudes of all the vectors in the universe change in a continuous fluent way because vectors act instantaneously.

figure 2

If there is locally an asymmetry between the universal electric field and the corresponding vectors of the magnetic field we cannot hypothesize that the quantum of energy is locally geometrical variable. So we have to conclude that local vectors don't reflect the topological deformation of the involved units always in a 100% corresponding way. Now what does this means?

Figure 2 shows a planet, the gravitational vectors (white lines) and the exponential topological deformation of the universal electric field caused by the gravitational vectors. It is vacuum space so the topological deformation corresponds with the gravitational vectors. In other words, we can describe the force of gravity at the macroscopic scale size with the help of the magnitudes of the gravitational vectors (Newton) or by the topological deformation of the universal electric field (Einstein).

figure 3

However, the origin of gravity is the decrease of the magnitude (radius) of one or more scalars of the Higgs field. That is why Newtonian gravity is a more accurate model than Einstein's “curved spacetime”. Because Einstein didn't described the volume of the universe, he described the macroscopic topology of the universal electric field around matter. Figure 3 shows in a schematic way the vector mechanism of Newtonian gravity in relation to figure 2 (Newtonian gravity as a push force from vacuum space around matter).

The image of the gravitational vectors shows that there is a constant dynamical equilibrium between all matter in the microcosm and macrocosm because of the generated vectors that are “locked” to the mass. It clarifies why the principle of non-locality acts instantaneous instead of an influence that is limited to the speed of light. Although [Newton's cradle](#) is a macroscopic object and the metal spheres are not 100% rigid it shows why the number of identical metal spheres don't significantly affect the immediately reaction of the last sphere in the row (mediation of vectors).

Figure 4 shows in a schematic way one unit of quantised space. Visible is the scalar (inscribed sphere), the schematic boundary of the unit, the vectors that correspond with the 12 points of contact with the adjacent scalars and the continuous topological deformation of the 12 faces of the unit (light blue arrows). A change of the shape of the unit (light blue arrows) results in a change of the scalar vectors (black arrows). The total amount of topological deformation during $1 t_q$ is fixed because in order to change its shape a unit has to transfer volume inside its boundary under influence of the active vectors of the scalar. The consequence is that the local asymmetry between the universal electric field and the corresponding magnetic field changes the direction of the topological deformation of the unit if the asymmetry is not equal distributed. In other words, it is an alteration of the symmetry between both corresponding fields.

figure 4

If a local concentration of energy without decreased scalars is created by involved units of quantised space the units around the centre of the concentration of energy are forced to deform like the units are part of a resultant circular motion. A concentration of energy cannot propagate linearly with the speed of light within the structure of quantised space. Because there is only one linear velocity in relation to energy changes: the speed of light.

figure 5

Figure 5 shows the resultant motion and it is clear that matter – rest mass – shows a different behaviour because of the vectorisation of the scalars of the flat Higgs field in vacuum space around.

The asymmetry between the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field is created by decreased scalars, actually “holes” in vector space (mediated vectors within the scalar lattice of the flat Higgs field). In other words, it is reasonable to suppose that rest mass and the asymmetry in some way are “entangled” at the smallest scale size.^[4] However, black holes are macroscopic celestial bodies and the source of an enormous amount of asymmetry between the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field. In other words, the local asymmetry of a rest mass carrying particle is not comparable with the asymmetry of a black hole.

This forces us to think about asymmetry in a way that is comparable with “building blocks” of asymmetry. An asymmetry that will manifest itself as basic local surpluses of vector magnitudes in relation to more and more complex configurations of these basic surpluses. It is tempting to compare these vector configurations with Plato’s theory of forms.

Conclusion

The existence of a deterministic universe where all the dynamical changes are synchronised doesn’t violate human experiences that seem to be not deterministic and even creations of free will. Because in phenomenological reality vectors act as hidden variables.

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08 The vector network

Recently there were articles in the media about the slow pace of the *human thoughts* and the related human verbal communication.^[1] This is an interesting issue because experiments in the past have shown that the human body is nearly “instantaneous” aware of changes in its direct environment although its awareness of – and its adaptation to – the immediate environment has a delay of about 200 - 300 milliseconds.

A couple of years ago there was an article about a well known awareness experiment. A person has to push a button at the moment he/she is aware of a new picture on the display of a computer. The body of the person is attached to sensors to measure the muscle tension, blood pressure, brain activity, etc., etc.^{[2][3]} The outcome is described above: our awareness of the change on the display has a delay of a number of milliseconds in relation to the registration of the change by our body.

The new experiment excluded every involvement of the psyche of the research team because the computer did the test and monitored all the changes, inclusive the choice at which moment a new image appeared on the display. The experiment confirmed the well known outcome of Benjamin Libet’s research. However, the 60 Hz refresh rate of a PC display is about 16,6 milliseconds. So what is it that the body of the test person detects? Because it is a really awkward idea that the human body waits until all the video data has arrived at the display and has build up the new image in 16,6 milliseconds. So what is triggering the human body to “signal” the change?

figure 1

All the changes in the universe – relational reality – are caused by the continuous redistribution of energy in quantised space. But the mutual influences between the units of

the structure of the universe are mediated by the scalars of the flat Higgs field in vacuum space. These influences act instantaneously because the mediated vectors don’t transfer energy. Vectors determine the direction of the topological deformation of the units of quantised space under invariant volume. Actually the synchronised redistribution of energy. Figure 1 shows a small part of the lattice of the Higgs field – diameter scalar about $0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m – and figure 2 shows the incredible complicated vector network inside the scalars. A network that fills the whole universe. All the vectors in the whole universe together can be thought as “vector space”.

figure 2

The new picture on the display of the test computer and the signalling human body represent related changes. Changes of energy in time and position. The coherence between these changes is the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field (vector space). We cannot hypothesize that the computer forced the test person to push the button because the computer transferred enough energy to the test person to accomplish the change. So it is reasonable to conclude that the correspondence between both changes originate mainly from the direct “physical” connection within vector space.

However the transfer of the data of a new image to the display is not the only change. The body of the test person was monitored with the help of sensors and related equipment. But the changes of the body of the test person were directly related with the change of the image on the display of the computer and not with other changes within all the electronic equipment around. Therefore it is reasonable to conclude that the concentration of the test person on the change of the picture on the display dominates the experiment. In some way the focus of the test person forced an “entangled” quantum state between the computer and his/her consciousness and body.

Concentration or focus is the direction of the human awareness. But humans can switch off the direction of the concentration. For example we can focus on the song of a nearby bird. But if we switch off the direction of the focus the song of the nearby bird becomes less prominent and the songs of the other birds from further around come more to the foreground. Actually we switched to a large environment instead of concentrating on a local phenomenon.

So general **consciousness** exists everywhere in the universe because consciousness cannot be local. Simply because relational reality is non-local (Nobel prize physics 2022). In other words, figure 2 shows the non-observable vector network of general consciousness and the human consciousness is part of it.

figure 3

The vector network that connects the points of contact of all the scalars of the Higgs field with equal magnitude ($r = 1,0$) is part of the 3D structure of the universe. Reports of people who had a near dead experience – search YouTube, I don't like cherry picking – describe super fast communication in the afterlife. There is no verbal communication because the exchange of information is telepathic. Phenomenological reality is described by entities in the afterlife as a 5-dimensional reality and it is not deterministic because humans have free will. Moreover, entities have the opinion that their “body” has not a fixed boundary like the body of people on the planet Earth.

Figure 3 shows that the generated vectors during the fixed transfer of 1 quantum of energy from one side of a unit to the opposite side are not quantised. Figure 4 shows in a schematic and simplified way the mutual influences of generated vectors by the universal electric field (topological deformation). Opposite vectors eliminate each other

if the magnitudes are identical. Vectors that point in opposite direction don't influence each other and the magnitudes of vectors in the same direction are added. But although vectors act instantaneous, it is the scalar mechanism of every unit of quantised space that creates all the vectors in the universe (figure 2).

figure 4

In other words, the afterlife is deterministic too and its geometrical properties are part of the 3-dimensional structure of the universe because the lattice of the Higgs field is 3-dimensional and part of the structure (inscribed spheres). So it seems that the entities in the afterlife are facing the same problem as humans on the planet Earth. They are convinced that relational reality in the afterlife exists by itself.

The supposed “unbearable slowness of being”^[1] is not really convincing because the human awareness of being is not slow. The exchange of information is slow and there is a delay in time between registering a change and the awareness of the change. If we use the method of verbal communication while we are thinking our thoughts are expressed in a sequence of words. But without words the expression of our imagination is not slow at all.

Conclusion

It is reasonable that the experience of all the changes in vector space is related with the existence of consciousness and awareness of all beings (inclusive plants, animals, etc.). However, we don't know if the phenomena at the smallest scale size have some kind of consciousness too. That means that the interactions of these phenomena show variances that don't rhyme with the expectations.

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09 The black hole

Is the effect of the asymmetry between the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field – caused by one or more decreased scalars of the Higgs field – significant at the smallest scale size? The question can be answered with the help of the black hole because the difference between a solitary rest mass carrying particle and a black hole is just the size. In other words this post is not about all the details of the properties of black holes, the topic is the creation of consciousness^[1] by the asymmetry mentioned above.

Not so long ago the consensus was that black holes are singularities. Personally I don't understand why theorists had this ridiculous idea. Because quantum field theory exclude this kind of hypotheses that are the result of extrapolations of the properties of an *emergent force* (gravity). However, the “visible” properties of black holes don't differ much from other celestial bodies, like heavy planets, stars and neutron stars. All these phenomena show – under certain conditions – accretion disks and (rudimentary) jets. So it is reasonable to think about a [black hole](#) as the most dense concentration of energy at the macroscopic scale size.

The consequence is that within the boundary of a black hole all the scalars of the Higgs field are decreased scalars. Therefore there are no 1D vectors to be find within its boundary. Nevertheless, every concentration of energy is forced to rotate because every change of a unit of quantised space during the constant of time ($1t_q$) has the speed of light. That is why every black hole has a steady rotation.^[2] Figure 1 shows a black hole, the resultant vectors of the Higgs field in vacuum space (red arrows), the increasing deformed units by the vectorisation of vacuum space around the black hole (rasterised concentric shells) and of

course the schematic units of quantised space. I have drawn these units really large because of the scalar vectors. And... to create “scale correspondence” with rest mass carrying particles.

figure 1

The force that is responsible for the creation of energy concentrations is the scalar mechanism of every unit. However, the decrease of 1 or more scalars of the Higgs field creates the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field around matter (red arrows). The consequence is that the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field around the black hole – inclusive the increasing deformation of the universal electric field towards the black hole – is an indissoluble part of the black hole.

The relational properties of the units of quantised space are known as the basic quantum fields in quantum field theory. These properties create “our” phenomenological reality and the consequence is that the structure of quantised space is the rest frame. So if we look at figure 1 we can imagine that the units are in rest and all the topological deformation – inclusive the resultant vectors (red) – are propagated in a certain direction. The cause behind the propagation is not a previous “action”, its cause is the scalar mechanism of all the units in the whole universe (non-local reality).

But if the black hole moves to the top of figure 1 all the units above the black hole are forced to deform more and more, inclusive the vectors of the corresponding magnetic field. While the units at the other side of the black will decrease their high amount of topological deformation during the propagation of the black hole in relation to the rest frame. Figure 2 shows the effect of the “push” of the black hole in the direction of the arrow in relation of the units in vacuum space around the black hole (the rest frame).

figure 2

In other words, the units in the red rasterised part are forced to increase their topological deformation, the units in the blue part decrease the deformation and in between is a neutral zone (transitional zone). This transitional zone is at right angles in respect to the direction of the motion of the black hole. In other words, the drawn vectors are the corresponding vectors of the magnetic field, created by the topological deformation of all the involved units under influence of the propagation of the black hole in vacuum space. Of course the topological deformation of the black hole is also propagated by the units of quantised space.

I can combine figure 1 and figure 2 and the result is figure 3. The image shows that the main vector direction in the transition zone is towards the black hole. That means that there is not much turbulence in relation to the “orbiting” quanta of the universal electric field. So it is clear why celestial bodies show accretion disks perpendicular to the direction of the motion of these bodies. Above and below the neutral transition zone there is no stable “orbit” possible (see the red and black vectors in figure 3).

figure 3

Within the boundary of the black hole – created by the vectorised Higgs field around (gravity) – there are no vectors because within the volume of the black hole all scalars are decreased scalars. That means that there are no points of contact between these scalars. As a result these scalars cannot mediate vectors.

However, all the units inside the black hole are much, much more deformed as the units in vacuum space around the black hole. That means that inside the black hole all the topological deformation is created the universal electric field (deformable part of the units). But the deformation doesn’t originate from inside, the deformation – the push – is created by an enormous amount of units around the black hole. Units that try to transfer a bit of their topological deformation to the centre of the concentration of deformation (the black hole). And last but not least, the created dipole by the motion of the black hole in relation to the rest frame – figure 2 – is also “attached” to the propagating black hole in vacuum space.

figure 4

It is for sure that all the topological deformation in figure 3 – inclusive the black hole itself – doesn’t violate the invariant volume of the units. But the magnitude of the *vectorised* scalars in vacuum space at the boundary of the black hole – figure 1 – cannot increase because the limit for every unit is just at “the inner edge” of the red line in figure 4. In other words, if the black hole is forced to accumulate more mass – decreasing the radii of the enclosed scalars even further – the magnitude of the vectorisation of the Higgs field itself doesn’t change. Only the amount of decreased scalars will grow.

The further increase of the “push” by all the units around the black hole is the scalar mechanism of the involved units around. That means that the gravitational force is a

composition of the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field because of decreased scalars and the further push by the universal electric field towards the centre of the concentration. A push that creates corresponding vectors of the magnetic field in vacuum space towards the black hole. Actually the vectors towards the black hole (red arrows in figure 1) represent a superposition of gravitational vectors and vectors of the magnetic field, generated by the topological deformation of the units in vacuum space around the black hole (electric field). But both type of vectors stop at the boundary of the black hole.

If energy is so much concentrated that one of more scalars decrease their radius, the involved decreased scalars stop mediating vectors. The created asymmetry between the points of contact of the scalars around the decreased scalars creates the vectorisation of the Higgs field around. That means that the total magnitude of the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field around is equal to the resistance against topological deformation of the not decreased scalar (red line in the diagram of figure 4). But the concentration of topological deformation has consequences (see figure 5).

figure 5

The left image and the right image have exactly the same amount of grey. Because the percentage black in each square of the right image is decreased with 1 point and the surplus is added to the units in the centre (like the law of conservation of energy).

So if energy is concentrated the amount of topological deformation of the units around decreases and therefore also the magnitude of the corresponding vectors of the magnetic field. It is reasonable to assume that at the moment a scalar is forced to decrease its radius the total magnitude of the vectorised flat Higgs field is equal to the total magnitude of the vectors of the involved units that point in the direction of the centre of the concentration of energy. Unfortunately every concentration of energy creates a circular transfer of topological deformation around the energy concentration. See figure 6.

figure 6

The consequence is that the vectors of the magnetic field towards the centre of the concentration of topological deformation don't represent all the corresponding vectors. Because a part of all the vectors are aligned ("pointing") around the concentration. Not only affecting the "freedom to deform in every direction"^[2] of the units in vacuum space but also affecting the magnitude distribution of the units. Because the total corresponding magnitude of the vectors of every unit in vacuum space during $1 t_q$ (constant of quantum time) is $\frac{1}{2} h$.

So effectively the increase of a "rotational" propagation of energy decreases the magnitude of the vectors of the magnetic field pointing towards the centre of a concentration of energy. In other words, an increase of mass results in a decrease of the corresponding influence of the magnetic field in the direction of the mass. And we can observe and detect this huge propagation of rotational energy around a concentration of matter in phenomenological reality. Like the creation of a protostar from a huge cloud of dust (figure 7).

figure 7

The white dotted line is to accentuate the existence and position of the protoplanetary disk.

The existence of the rotational propagation of energy around matter shows the asymmetry between the local density of the universal electric field in relation to the amount of concentrated energy. Because if a lot of dust (matter) is propagated towards a black hole the velocity of the dust particles nears the speed of light and the result is the emission of electromagnetic radiation.

That is why we are aware of the existence of the accretion disk and the 2 jets in line with the rotation axis of the black hole. But without the infalling dust the accretion disk and the 2 jets still exist “unchanged” although these phenomena of rotational propagation of energy don’t emit electromagnetic radiation.

Conclusion

Every concentration of energy creates rotational propagation of energy in vacuum space. The concentration of energy (rest mass) creates also a dipole of vectors of the magnetic field because of the propagation of the rest mass in relation to the rest frame (figure 2). Not only in the macrocosm but also in the microcosm. Both mechanism will create all kinds of mutual interferences (“relative stable turbulences”) in vacuum space that seem to be “decoupled” from the concentration of energy itself (e.g. the black hole). However, these influences create the conditions but don’t clarify the experience of being a local consciousness.

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10 Dark matter

Recently I saw an interview about a new hypothesis that the supposed particles that mediate the gravitational force – gravitons – have mass too. So the hypothesis was nicknamed “heavy gravity”. There were some speculations in the comments about the relation between Dark matter and consciousness too. Inclusive a relation between these heavy gravitons and Dark energy. So maybe it is wise to

describe these phenomena with the help of quantised space (so the next post is about Dark energy).

In cosmology the dominant force between all the large celestial structures is gravity. That is really problematic because gravity is an emergent force. Because without matter there exist no gravity; not in Einstein’s theory of [General relativity](#)^[1] and not in [Newtonian gravity](#).^[2] In quantum field theory all the phenomena – inclusive matter – are created by the basic quantum fields.^[3] So if cosmologists speculate about the start of the observable universe ([ΛCDM](#)) its existence is a creation by the basic quantum fields that existed already everywhere in the universe.

These basic quantum fields interact with each other and within their individual structure, like the continuous redistribution of energy everywhere in the universe within the structure of the universal electric field. The concept of quantised space – described by [Parmenides of Elea](#) some 2500 years ago – unifies these basic quantum fields into one spatial structure that is the volume of the universe.

figure 1

Dark matter is what astronomers have termed [Dark matter](#). It originate from the observation that the velocities of the nearby stars around the sun are not in line with their amount of mass ([Jan Hendrik Oort](#)). Soon it was observed too that the rotational velocity of spiral galaxies doesn’t correspond with the mass of the stars further away from the centre of the galaxy either (figure 1). The image shows a galaxy with Dark matter (left) and one without at the right. The same rotational velocity in the centre of both galaxies but a higher rotational velocity at the outskirts of a galaxies with Dark matter.

There are papers that suggest alternative theories of gravitation (like [MOND](#)) but astronomers have argued that the observations of colliding clusters of galaxies – like the

[Bullet cluster](#) in figure 2 – are not in line with these alternative theories of gravitation.

The blue colour in the image of the Bullet cluster shows Dark matter. That seems crazy because we cannot observe Dark Matter. The blue colour represents *calculated* Dark matter. Because the light of galaxies further away – behind the region of the Bullet cluster – shows a weak form of [gravitational lensing](#). That means that the light of these further away galaxies is dispersed a bit because of an invisible amount of mass (Dark matter) in between these galaxies and the observer: the dark matter of the bullet cluster.

Of course there are other observations that are in line with the supposed existence of Dark matter but the deviant rotational velocity of spiral galaxies and the observation of colliding galaxy clusters are significant examples.

figure 2

Gravitational lensing was predicted by Albert Einstein because of his hypothesis that matter curves the geometry of space itself. However, it is not possible that the volume of space can curve if about 74% of the volume of the universe is “occupied” by the scalars of the Higgs field. The scalars together form a rigid lattice of spheres (the flat Higgs field) because the sphere is the only 3D geometrical object that is a true scalar. The consequence is that Einstein’s curved space envelopes only about 26% of the whole volume of the universe.

Unfortunately this 26% of the volume of the universe is not spacetime but it represents the volume of the structure of the universal electric field. So it is easy to conclude that Einstein’s theory of General relativity is not a better description of the “tangible” properties of Newton’s [absolute space](#). In other words, Einstein’s theory of General relativity is about the influence of matter on the topology of the structure of the universal electric field. That is obvious be-

cause matter is concentrated energy and energy is the variable property of the topology of the universal electric field.

Now we face the problem that cosmologists and physicists have the opinion that the properties of large structures in the universe are determined by Einstein’s theory of General relativity. That implies that matter curves space(time). So there is the hypothesis that Dark matter is the result of an enormous amount of weak interacting massive particles ([WIMPs](#)) in the universe. But massive particles are rest mass carrying particles so every WIMP must “envelope” decreased scalars of the Higgs field too. Experiments to detect the existence of WIMPs are not successful, because Dark matter is only detectable in an indirect way by astronomical observations.

If Einstein’s theory of General relativity describes the deformation of the universal electric field under influence of Newtonian gravitational vectors the question arises why we cannot detect Dark matter in our solar system. Because Dark matter is not a fantasy of astronomers. The Bullet cluster shows the evidence of its existence as a “tangible” energy phenomenon.

“Dark matter”

If mass is a concentration of energy within the structure of the universal electric field ($E = m c^2$) it is evidently that there must be some kind of a “power” to concentrate free energy (E) within the structure. The mechanism is described in previous posts and I have termed it the *scalar mechanism*. Because in geometry every unit of quantised space can be interpreted as a decreased scalar under influence of all the other units that tessellate the volume of the universe.

This type of concentrated free energy doesn’t emit electromagnetic waves like matter. Because concentrated free energy represents just a local energy density. It isn’t stable like a rest mass carrying particle so the energy density is comparable with local amplitudes. And amplitudes are everywhere in vacuum space.^[4]

If the scalar mechanism of a large number of units of quantised space have concentrated so much energy that one of more scalars of the local flat Higgs field decrease their magnitude, the concentration of energy can increase further and the result is the concentrated energy of a rest mass carrying particle. But it is obvious that the scalar mechanism of every unit of quantised space doesn’t stop trying to minimise the surface area of the unit.

figure 3

However, the continuous energy transformations in the universe are not unlimited. The total amount of energy is conserved and the total amount of corresponding vectors too. That means that the linear propagation of 1 quantum of energy is equal to the speed of light and the linear propagation of the corresponding vectors is instantaneous. The consequence is that vectors will stabilise local energy densities between large distances long before these energy densities can interfere with each other by exchanging energy. In other words, the non-locality of gravitational vectors facilitate the direction of the propagation of the local energy concentrations – like celestial bodies – in vacuum space.

Because the scalar mechanism of every unit don't stop to minimise the surface area of every unit the deformable part of every units continue to concentrate energy (topological deformation). So there exists some kind of an average increase of created matter in the universe. More or less in line with the general idea of the lambda cold dark matter model.

However, concentrations of energy that cannot transform into rest mass can be compared with fog. There is a higher amount of average energy density (topological deformation) but it will not transform into matter in the short term. So there is no difference between real matter and Dark matter because the underlying mechanism for both phenomena is energy concentration. The consequence is that we find this “fog” of higher concentrated free energy around matter. Especially around celestial structures like star systems, galaxies and clusters of galaxies.

The force of gravity

The concentration of matter is the result of gravitational vectors from vacuum space around. Actually the vectorisation of the flat Higgs field in vacuum space because of the decreased scalars in the centre of matter. But the concentration of free energy by the universal

electric field is still active because of the scalar mechanism of every unit of quantised space.

The gravitational constant is measured in our solar system. The sun emits a continuous amount of energy (electromagnetic radiation and particles) thus there are no regions of increased energy density (Dark matter) in our solar system to be find. Simply because there is too much disturbance of the universal electric field in vacuum space around the sun. That means that the measured gravitational constant (G) represents only the influence of the vectors of Newtonian gravity. In between the star systems there is Dark matter and of course also in the outer regions of a galaxy.

Figure 4 shows in the centre a spiral galaxy. The black arrows symbolise the concentration of free energy during the evolution of the galaxy and the blue arrows the gravitational vectors because of the created matter. In other words, the creation of a galaxy “out of vacuum space” needs a much, much larger volume of involved units than the volume of the galaxy itself.

figure 4

The velocity of a rest mass carrying particle is determined by the amount of topological deformation of the particle itself in relation to the average deformation of vacuum space around. That means that if we increase the average amount of deformation (energy) in vacuum space around, the propagation of the particle from position I to position II needs less time ($n \times 1t_q$). The consequence is that the existence of Dark matter in between star systems and at the outskirts of galaxies speeds up the rotational velocity of the

star systems further away from the centre of a galaxy. Not because Dark matter is massive (like WIMPs) but because it represents an increase of the average energy density of vacuum space (see figure 1).

Conclusion

Dark matter is what Einstein called “mass”. A less dense concentration of free energy in relation to rest mass (matter). Nevertheless, because of its large volume, the mass of Dark matter has linear momentum too. That is why figure 2 shows that Dark matter (blue) continuous its motion in front of the colliding matter of the galaxies of both clusters (pink colour). So it is difficult to imagine that there is a direct relation between Dark matter and general consciousness.

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11 Dark energy

The previous post was about gravity and its relation with the existence of Dark matter. There were some speculations that Dark matter and Dark energy are related. This post clarifies the underlying relation.

The idea that the observable universe expands, originates from the observation that the light of distant galaxies is red shifted. The further away the [galaxy](#), the more the light of the distant galaxy is red shifted ([Hubble’s law](#)). Astronomers first assumed that the red shift was caused by the

motion of the galaxies away from the observer. In physics this type of red shift of electromagnetic waves is called the [Doppler effect](#). In 1845 the effect in relation to sound waves was examined by the Dutch meteorologist Buys Ballot with the help of a passing train and the sound at a continuous frequency by a trumpet. There is a [painting](#) of the experiment on a wall of a house next to the railway where the experiment was done. On my way to the dentist in Utrecht, the Netherlands, I see the wall painting. It is on [StreetView](#) too ;-)

However, better telescopes showed that the amount of red shift became so dominant in relation to the frequency of the light of nearby galaxies that the most distant galaxies had to move with a velocity higher than the speed of light.

So it was clear that the cosmological redshift was not caused by the velocity of the motion of the galaxies (Doppler effect). If space can curve under influence of matter – Einstein’s theory of General relativity – it is not so far-fetched to assume that space can also expand “around matter”. Because the expansion of vacuum space clarifies the lengthen of the wave length of the emitted electromagnetic waves by far away galaxies. The direct relation between the non-Doppler red shift and the expansion of space can be calculated because of the existence of standard-candles ([cosmic distant ladder](#)).

Unfortunately better measurements showed that the non-Doppler redshift is not 100% linear. There is observational evidence that the red shift increases during the evolution of the universe. That means that our present universe [expands faster](#) in comparison with the expansion of the universe during a same period of time in the past. That is impossible without some kind of energy and that is why the cause behind the accelerated expansion is termed “[Dark energy](#)”. Because we don’t know the origin of this enormous amount of energy.

Note that the entire theoretical framework is build upon the assumption that Einstein’s theory of General relativity is correct and quantum field theory is not applicable at the macroscopic scale size. And last but not least, astronomers and cosmologists are convinced that our universe is isotropic and homogeneous.^[1]

Quantised space

If there exists no non-Doppler red shift of the light of distant galaxies nobody had speculated about the existence of a [big-bang](#) as the start of our universe. Cosmologists had

explored a steady state universe – a continuum – as suggested by Newton’s axioms about [absolute space and time](#). In other words, if the non-Doppler redshift of the light of distant galaxies doesn’t originate from the expansion of vacuum space, most of the conceptual framework of the Standard cosmological model ([\$\Lambda\$ CDM](#)) is obsolete. Therefore it is reasonable to start with the examination of the hypothesis that the non-Doppler redshift is caused by the expansion of vacuum space “itself”.

figure 1

Recent observations with the [JWST](#) have showed that the amount of available energy in the primordial universe was much higher than today. Actually it is in line with the assumption of the Λ CDM that the amount of cold Dark matter – concentrated free energy (see previous post) – was more abundant in the early universe. The evolution of the first UV-bright galaxies – about 300 million years old like the galaxy [JADES-GS-z13-1-LA^{\[2\]}](#) – has showed that the rate of the evolution in the early universe was not equal to what we see today nearby our own galaxy, the Milky Way. So what is the mechanism behind this observation?

Figure 1 shows in a *schematic* way the structure of the volume of the universe. So it doesn’t mean that our universe is tessellated with real cubes because the image represents the geometrical foundations of our universe. That means that the structure must have a metric (l_c), it must tessellate the volume of the universe – build up by smaller units with invariant volumes – and every unit of the structure must have identical basic properties.

Figure 2 shows a part of the lattice of the scalars of the Higgs field. The Higgs field exists everywhere in the universe and it is undeniable that the Higgs field has a structure. So if I relate figure 1 with figure 2 it is reasonable to suppose that every unit must have some kind of an internal spherical shape forming mechanism inside. The only real

3D scalar is the sphere so it is easier to use the term *scalar mechanism*.

figure 2

In macroscopic reality the strength of a material spherical shape depends on the closed boundary (shell) and the size of the boundary. That means that I can express the internal build up of the scalar mechanism of every unit with the help of an infinite amount of concentric shells. Each shell with a slightly larger radius. See figure 3.

Figure 2 shows 2 different configurations of sphere packing ([Kepler’s conjecture](#)). I have drawn both configurations in figure 3. The spheres are drawn in cross section so the imaginary “shell structure” – concentric shells – is visible. Showing the large differences between the empty space in between the scalars of both configurations.

figure 3

But in spite of this all, the units of quantised space – figure 1 – tessellate the whole volume of the universe. The consequence is that every unit must be a deformed scalar to “drive out” empty space. But figure 3 shows that pressing the spheres together cannot fill the empty spaces in between the spheres in a symmetrical way. The latter means that the result represents a geometrical shape that have identical faces. Like figure 4.

The image shows a [rhombic dodecahedron](#). It can tessellate space and if I duplicate the object many times I can build the scalar lattice in figure 2 with the inscribed spheres of

figure 4

these identical rhombic dodecahedra. However, figure 3 shows that pushing identical spheres together cannot result in the creation of identical rhombic dodecahedra. Because half way the compression of the spheres the empty space in between the blue spheres in figure 3 is totally filled with the volume of deformed shells while there is still empty space between the brown spheres. The consequence is that there is a displacement of the volume of the outer shells in relation to the build up of the internal scalar mechanism at the start. Figure 5 explains why.

figure 5

The volume of every unit is invariant. So if the deformed volume of a unit is pushed to one side – the green arrow in figure 5 – its deformed volume will effect the unit at the left in exactly the same way (red arrow). Moreover, this simple example of topological deformation shows that the increase of the surface area of the unit in the centre is equal to the surface area of the “bare part” of the scalar inside the unit. That is why we have to conclude that the surface area of the deformed part of the unit is invariant too. At least if all the units around have scalars inside with identical radii.

So I can draw the conclusion that the deformed part of the unit still has some kind of a homogeneous structure (equal density of its deformed volume). Now back to the situation during the compression of the spheres in figure 3.

If the radius of the inscribed sphere (scalar) of all the units with a flat scalar field is $r = 1,0$ the radius of the undistorted spheres in figure 3 is $r = 1,105$. See figure 6.

figure 6

Radius $r = 1,0$ is the situation that all the empty space in between the brown spheres in figure 3 is filled too. So less than half way the compression of the spheres in figure 3 the empty space in between the blue spheres is filled. That is the black dotted line in figure 6.

Deforming the volume of the spheres in figure 3 even further will create a not equal distribution of the scalar mechanism inside the scalar itself. Because the deformed scalar mechanism at the dotted black line has already filled the empty space in between the blue spheres but the space in between the brown spheres is not totally filled (red line).

The consequence is that the deformed part of the volume cannot fill all the empty space in between the compressed spheres in a symmetrical way, like the symmetry in fig. 4.

figure 7

But what I have described above about the asymmetry of the scalar mechanism (figure 7) is the usual geometrical reality of the universal electric field – the deformed part of every unit – and the corresponding vectors mediated by the points of contact between the scalars (figure 2 and figure 7). See the descriptions in reference 3 and/or 4. In other words, the amount of surface area of every unit of quantised space “at the supposed start of the universe” is larger

than the surface area of a rhombic dodecahedron with exactly the same volume.

The amount of volume of every unit is identical and invariant. The consequence is that the difference between the average amount of surface area of all the units and the surface area of this rhombic dodecahedron represents the amount of energy *that is constantly redistributed between all the units of quantised space*.

The topological deformation (energy) of every unit during the constant of quantum time (t_q) is synchronised and therefore the topological deformation is quantised (the Planck constant h). The scalar mechanism of every unit tries to minimise the surface area of the unit. Thus a local concentration of energy is only possible if a large amount of units transferred some of their individual topological deformation to the local concentration. Just set theory.

Dark energy

The linear propagation of a quantum of energy within the structure of the universal electric field is the speed of light (c). Figure 8 shows the diagram of an electromagnetic wave and the x-vector shows the direction of the electromagnetic wave in vacuum space. The wave form represents the action/reaction of the quantum of energy in relation to the topological deformation of the units around.

figure 8

If more and more units of quantised space transfer a part of their topological deformation to local concentrations of energy (matter) the amount of topological deformation of the units in vacuum space decreases.

The consequence is that the action/reaction of vacuum space decreases too. In other words, if a photon (figure 8) was emitted 13,7 billion years ago and its wave length is measured now the wave length has increased (red shifted).

Thus the origin of the non-Doppler red shift of the light of distant galaxies doesn't originate from the expansion of vacuum space. It is the result of the continuous concentration of energy by the scalar mechanism of all the units of quantised space.

During the evolution of the universe the surplus of surface area between the average surface area of the units and the surface area of the rhombic dodecahedron gets smaller and smaller. That means that the concentration of the same amount of energy will cost more time than 13,7 billion years ago. Because the number of involved units to create the same mass have to increase.

That is what astronomers observe in relation to the rate of the birth of new stars during the [evolution of the galaxies](#). It shows a decreasing rate of energy concentration towards the present. In other words the non-Doppler red shift has increased. Therefore, the increase of the wave length of the non-Doppler redshift is not linear with the increase of the trajectory of the electromagnetic wave. Because the speed of light is a universal constant.

Conclusion

The term "Dark energy" is misleading. Because the increase of the observed non-Doppler redshift of the light of distant galaxies during the evolution of the universe is caused by the decrease of free energy in vacuum space. A deficit of energy that is equal to the local surplus of energy by matter. That is why vacuum space doesn't expand and the non-linearity between the red shift and the length of the trajectory of light is the consequence of the concentration of energy in our universe.

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12 Experiences

Although phenomenological physics is the science about energy in all its “tangible” manifestations, the reductionism of relational reality cannot clarify our daily experiences as human beings. Not at least because our thoughts are dominated by the phenomenological point of view, the search for cause and effect. The consequence is that the physics text books are not really helpful to understand the underlying reality of relational reality.

One of the hypotheses to interpret relational reality at the quantum level is the [many-worlds interpretation](#) (MWI) in Quantum mechanics (QM). The problem with the hypothesis is that the volume of our universe has to be “transparent” for all these existing realities. The problem is a bit comparable with the idea that the direction of time (change) is twofold. It “flows” in the direction of the future and “at the same time” it flows in the direction of the past.

These ideas are founded on the assumption that our universe has no “tangible” properties. That means basic properties of nature that create relational reality. Because the consequence of both ideas is that the volume of our universe is filled with an infinite amount of different versions of our universe. But it is without doubt that we don’t experience the existence of these infinite versions of our universe in daily live. Not to speak about all the measurement instruments that fail to detect all these versions of our universe at the moment the instruments are active.

I don’t criticise the many-worlds interpretation in Quantum mechanics. I even wrote a paper about its origin.^[1] However, the QM hypothesis originates from [mathematical abstractions](#) to describe simplified quantum reality with the help of multidimensional vector space ([Hilbert space](#)). But the problem is that Quantum mechanics has no “tangible” foundations.^[2] It is a mathematical framework to calculate the electromagnetic wave structure of relational reality to mimic the outcome of measurement instruments.

In the third post I mentioned [a book](#) of [Emanuel Swedenborg](#) about the inhabitants of different planets in our solar system and even from another star system. Although his book about the afterlife, [Heaven and Hell](#), is the best known. It is difficult to determine the spiritual mechanism behind Swedenborg’s capacity to experience “non-tangible” reality ([out-of-body experiences](#)). Nevertheless the description of his experiences/observations are clear and the contents reflect his scientific mind.

In his book about the afterlife of inhabitants of planets of the solar system, he describes some “physics” of their existence in the space of our solar system. In other words, it is not about heaven or hell, it seems to be some kind of an “in between” state. Swedenborg described that all these non-material persons could not see the planets of the solar system. Their experience of reality originates from their personal memories, although they were aware of the presence of other non-material persons and communicated in a direct way ([telepathic communication](#)).

By the way, the inhabitants of the other planets in the solar system – Mercury, Venus, the Moon, Mars and Jupiter – are “half” material and/or non-material. The descriptions of their home planets – inclusive the plants and animals – are not in line with what our measurement instruments observe (satellites). Besides that, I once read the observation that “Ufo’s” that are visible near the surface of the planet Earth become invisible the further these “crafts” move away from the planet. It suggests that the visibility has a direct relation with the density gradient of the electromagnetic field around celestial bodies.

Swedenborg described that he could not see the bright radiation of the sun either. If he turned in the direction of the sun he saw some kind of a fuzzy dark spot. That is reasonable because light is a property of atoms; the emission and absorption of electromagnetic waves ($E = hf$). Non-material persons (consciousnesses) cannot absorb emitted electromagnetic waves, at least not in the visible frequencies. But why did Swedenborg described the sun as a “fuzzy dark spot”? There is just one reasonable clarification. It is because the sun blocks most of the vectors of the magnetic field.

figure 1

Swedenborg visited another star system too. The [nearest star](#) is about 4,5 light years away but the duration of his voyage to this star system was about 2 weeks. It indicates that non-material consciousness has a direct relation with vector fields. Because vectors are not limited to the speed of light (c), vectors act instantaneous.

Of course there are many, many interpretations of the “physics” of non-material reality. Just search YouTube with terms like channelling, psychic medium, remote viewing or even Ufo/UAP. It will result in a large amount of different opinions or even fantasies that describe a reality that is for certain not equal to what we experience in daily live. Fortunately, the descriptions of the non-material reality by Emanuel Swedenborg give some support to understand the underlying mechanism. And that is really interesting.

The image in figure 1 shows in a schematic way the magnetic dipole that is created by the propagation of a [black hole](#) in quantised space. That means that the structure of the units is in rest – the rest frame of the universe – and the black hole propagates within and by the properties of the structure. We can replace the black hole with a rest mass carrying particle and the general structure of the image still stands. We can replace it by a galaxy too. Figure 2 shows it in a schematic way (the black dot is the dominant black hole in the centre of the galaxy)

figure 2

If general consciousness is a property of vector space, then I have to conclude that figure 1 shows some kind of a “habitable atmosphere” (shelter) in terms of vector space. It even shows Swedenborg’s differentiation about the 3 main regions in the afterlife.

Figure 1 shows a neutral transformation zone (grey) with 2 separate large regions that represent partly different experiences. I don’t like the terms “heaven” and “hell” but it is for sure that the red region is the opposite of the blue region in relation to the direction of the vectors.

Swedenborg’s communication with non-material persons in our solar system is in line with the existence of the neutral or transition zone perpendicular to the direction of the motion of the Milky Way. That means that the 2 large regions (red and blue) are positioned above and below the plane (yellow) of the galaxy (figure 2). I am not surprised because sometimes Swedenborg uses descriptions about both regions that show some resemblance with the nature of fractals.^[3] A concept that wasn’t known in the period that Swedenborg lived.

What does this mean for the existence of the individual consciousness of the phenomena in the universe? Aside from the fact that consciousness will exist on every scale size. Because what is going on in between the start and the end of the propagation of one quantum of topological deformation (energy).

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13 Beyond quantum time

In theoretical physics there are different interpretations of the nature of time. These interpretations originate from different theories. Time as a fixed quantity of duration originate from quantum field theory and time as a variable originate from Einstein’s theory of Special relativity. However, both different interpretations describe the changes of energy within the structure of the universal electric field. But the universal electric field has a corresponding vector field, the magnetic field. Vectors act instantaneous so in between the duration of the constant of quantum time there exist the experience of instantaneous vector time.

The constant of quantum time (t_q) has a duration of $\approx 5,99 \times 10^{-23}$ second. It is the period of time for 1 quantum of energy to be propagated over a distant that is equal to the minimal length scale ($\ell_c \approx 0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m). The minimal

length scale is equal to the length (cross-section) of the unit of quantised space. The velocity of the propagation of a quantum of energy is about $300.000 \text{ km} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ so it is easy to calculate the constant of quantum time.

Figure 1 shows a diagram that represents the increase of the topological deformation of a unit of quantised space with just 1 quantum of energy (h). The increase of the surface area of the deformable part of the unit – actually the universal electric field – creates corresponding vectors within the scalar of the unit, part of the flat Higgs field in vacuum space. These corresponding vectors are represented by the red arrows in figure 1. If the unit has a decreased scalar, the unit has no vectors because there are no points of contact between the scalar and the scalars of the adjacent units.^{[1][2]}

figure 1

The deformation of the unit in the diagram doesn't differentiate between the input deformation ($\frac{1}{2} h$) by adjacent units and the output deformation ($\frac{1}{2} h$) toward other adjacent units. The schematic figure 2 – a simplification of the topological deformation between 3 units – corresponds with the diagram in figure 3. The green arrow is input deformation and the red arrow is output deformation, of course in relation to the scalar mechanism of the unit in the middle.

The deformation of the unit is the result of the *internal* transfer of a flux of infinite small volumes because the whole volume of the unit is invariant. That means that the sum of the magnitudes of all the generated vectors – because of the quantum of energy – is equal to the transferred flux of volume inside the unit. Note that the schematic figure 2 shows that the increase and decrease of the surface area of the unit – because of the topological deformation –

is actually the increase and decrease of the surface area of the “bare” part of the scalar. The geometrical consequence is that the surface area of the deformed part of the unit is invariant *in vacuum space* (flat Higgs field).

figure 2

A unit cannot change the *direction* of its internal transfer of volume during $1 t_q$ ($5,99 \times 10^{-23}$ second). The simplified situation in figure 2 proves it in a geometrical way. In other words, figure 1 shows only the quantum of energy and the corresponding sum of the generated vectors by the increase of the surface area of the unit with 1 quantum of energy.

In vacuum space every scalar of the Higgs field has exactly the same magnitude (radius) so if a unit has the shape of a rhombic dodecahedron every vector inside the scalar has exactly the same magnitude at the 12 points of contact with the adjacent scalars. See figure 3. It means that the 12 drawn vectors represent the “push” of the scalar mechanism towards all the other scalars around where the Higgs field is flat (every scalar has exactly the same radius). In other words, the drawn vectors in figure 3 only represent the scalar mechanism of the *not deformed* part of the unit.

figure 3

Because of the scalar mechanism of the unit – synchronised with all the other units in the universe – there is “automatically” a new fixed amount of topological deformation during the next $1 t_q$. The new deformation of the shape of the unit is determined by the influence of the magnitudes of all the vectors within the flat Higgs field. I have visualised the changes of the deformable part of the unit in vacuum space with green arrows (input deformation) and red arrows (output deformation). The result is figure 4 and the

drawn schematic shape is the rhombic dodecahedron. In reality it is a deformed rhombic dodecahedron (deformed around the points of contact with the adjacent scalars).

The unit in figure 4 can only deform with 1 fixed amount of topological deformation (h) during $1 t_q$, no matter the sum of the absolute magnitudes of the involved vectors. In other words, the topological deformation represented by the green and red arrows shows only the relative change of the vectors during $1 t_q$. The example of the topological deformation in the image is divided over the 12 faces of the unit (6 input faces and 6 output faces). During $1 t_q$ every unit changes its shape with a fixed amount of topological deformation that is equal to the Planck constant (h). But the input deformation (green arrows) is done by 6 adjacent units. So if we want to assign the amount of topological deformation that each unit “creates” during $1 t_q$, the actual amount of topological deformation is $\frac{1}{2} h$.

figure 4

The nature of the mechanism to concentrate energy – actually the scalar mechanism of the unit pushing against adjacent units – is always outwards. A unit cannot contract its shape into a shape that is more symmetrical than its shape a moment before. The volume of every unit is invariant so all the changes of the shape of the units during $1 t_q$ are synchronised. So if there is a huge amount of topological deformation somewhere in vacuum space – like a black hole – its influence on everything around doesn’t originate from the black hole itself. It is vacuum space around that “pushes” (concentrates) topological deformation to the centre of the enormous volume of the involved units.

The diagram in figure 1 shows an increase of surface area of the universal electric field and the corresponding increase of the magnitudes of the vectors of the magnetic field. In between the start and the end of the topological deformation during $1 t_q$ the universal electric field cannot change *the direction* of the topological deformation (red

and green arrows) and it cannot change *the amount* of the ongoing topological deformation. Just because the volume of every unit of quantised space is invariant. However, the involved vectors (red arrows in the diagram of figure 1) don’t stop to change their magnitudes under influence of the topological deformation.

However, the total amount of change of the magnitudes of the involved vectors – in relation to one unit – cannot exceed or being less than the fixed amount of topological deformation during $1 t_q$.

Conclusion

In between the constant of quantum time ($1 t_q$) – the fixed amount of topological deformation – there is a continuous alteration of the magnitudes of the vectors of the magnetic field within the flat Higgs field (“vector space”).

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14 Displaced vectors

Humans have the awareness of an existence of a not linear time. An awareness that is not in line with the existence of the constant of quantum time ($1 t_q$). It seems to defy cause and effect and give raise to the experience that humans have some kind of free will. The feeling that an amount of “will power” can change the phenomenological world that surrounds us. Actually relational reality.

In vacuum space the deformation of a unit of quantised space is limited to the spots around the points of contact of the scalar of the unit and the scalars of the adjacent units around. Figure 1 shows the topological deformation between 2 units (left side). Drawn is the cross section, the face of the right unit and at the right hand a larger cross section ($r_{is} = 1.0$ is the radius of every scalar where the Higgs field is flat).

The “nature” of the scalar can be described as the not deformed part of the scalar mechanism of the unit (I). So its resistance against the deformation by the scalar mechanism

of the other units around is active in the points of contact with the adjacent scalars. It can be described with the help of vectors (II). However, the scalar mechanism itself is a spherical shape forming mechanism so the scalar represents also the concept of a sphere that is build up by infinite small concentric shells (III), a bit comparable with the layers of an onion. Figure 2 shows the 3 descriptions.

figure 1

If we imagine the decrease of a scalar under influence of the “push” by a large amount of involved units – for example the scalar in figure 2, image II – the question arises how much surface area of the unit is involved.

Theoretically, *each* unit can not transfer more topological deformation than $\frac{1}{2}$ quantum of energy during the constant of quantum time ($1 t_q$). Although it is hard to imagine what is exactly going on because of the different “velocities” between the quantum of energy (c) and a vector ($> c$).

figure 2

Figure 3 shows in a schematic way a rest mass carrying particle (black) with a decreased scalar inside (red). Because of the decreased scalar the adjacent scalars and all the other scalars around the adjacent scalars get vectorised. Simply because the 12 points of contact of each of the 12 adjacent scalars are reduced to 11 points of contact, creating an asymmetrical distribution of the undistorted scalar mechanism of these units. Just imagine that in figure 2 II one vector disappears. It is obvious that this will create an unbalance inside the scalar.

figure 3

The unbalance creates *resulting* vectors in vacuum space around (red arrows) and these vectors determine the topological deformation of the units around (rasterised concentric shells). This increasing topological deformation towards the particle is equal to the local energy density of the universal electric field (QFT). The vectors in figure 3 are resulting vectors, because the red arrows represent more than 1 vector of the unit. Like the real shape of the units is not cubic either.

Every unit transforms its shape with the same amount of topological deformation if we express the deformation with the help of the transferred internal volume to acquire the next shape. In between there is deformation too but we can only measure the change of the direction of the topological deformation (the cause behind the existence of the Planck constant). Because of the synchronisation of the changes of the shape of every unit of quantised space a measurement instrument (and our senses) cannot “signal” the transfer of the flux of infinite small volume inside every unit. That is why for measurement instruments and for humans phenomenal reality is limited to relational reality.

The consequence is that during $1 t_q$ (constant of quantum time) all the involved units in figure 3 transform in such a way that the observer thinks that the particle had moved a little bit in relation to the rest frame of quantised space (the schematic cubic grid). Of course, the observer doesn’t see that the whole volume – the particle and the topological deformation of all the other involved units around – has moved as a whole. The consequence is that the velocity of the rest mass is determined by the amount of quanta that has to be transferred to “move” the particle and everything around from 1 unit to an adjacent unit.

figure 4

The image in figure 3 shows just 1 rest mass carrying particle. If I draw 2 particles – see figure 4 – the local conditions are quite different. Because the symmetrical distribution of vectors around each particle is disturbed by the other particle (decreased scalars cannot mediate vectors).

The effect on both particles is a push from vacuum space around (red) that influences the direction of the propagation of both particles in relation to the rest frame. However, the vectorisation (red arrows in figure 3) originate from the decreased scalar. The consequence is that the sum of the magnitude of the vectors of each particle is a bit comparable with a constant. Although the average properties of vacuum space around influence the size of the volume that can be thought as “vectorised space” (the red arrows that point towards each particle).

However the sum of the magnitudes of all the vectors in the universe is conserved, like all the energy changes in the universe are conserved. In other words, figure 4 shows that the existence of matter *at every scale size* results in the existence of “displaced vectors” (see previous post).

Conclusion

The emergence of matter in the universe started the creation of relative independent configurations of local displaced vectors. It doesn’t mean that the correspondence between the universal electric field and the magnetic field was lost. It changed the symmetry between the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field into an asymmetrical correspondence. The emergence of another type of interference between both fields that is termed “live” in our scientific culture.

15 Energy densities

For humans phenomenological reality is dominated by matter. Our senses are comparable with measurement instruments so it is natural for us that sensorial reality is “tangible” reality. But in science we search for the origin of consciousness and near dead experiences (NDE) seem to be part of it. So there are indications that the human consciousness can exist without a material body. It questions the idea that live – consciousness – needs a material world like we know it.

Like I wrote in a post [before](#) I read [Emanuel Swedenborg’s](#) books when I was young (around the age of 26) but I couldn’t buy his book about live on planets and other star systems. Fortunately about a decade ago I found out that there was an online translation of the book so I immediately start reading the book. This book [De Telluribus in Mundo nostro Solari](#) describes the thoughts of Emanuel Swedenborg about deceased inhabitants (“ghosts”) of planets of our solar system and his conversations with these inhabitants in their afterlife. Emanuel Swedenborg had described in his book about Heaven and Hell that the afterlife represents 3 “territories”: “the in between state”, the hell and the heaven. It is clear that his book about the (deceased) inhabitants of the solar system and another star system is about non-material live in the *in between state*, close nearby their planets. See the post [Experiences](#).

Note that the experiences of Emanuel Swedenborg originate from the second part of his live – see Wikipedia – and that Emanuel Swedenborg doesn’t describe his personal observations of the planets itself. He is only aware of what is available in the memories of these “ghosts” (entities).

Without a material body the emission and absorption of electromagnetic waves in the visible spectrum is not observable. So what he describes is the situation on these planets that exist in the memories of the deceased inhabitants for at least 300 – 350 years in the past. By the way, Emanuel Swedenborg was the first European scientist who speculated in his book Principia (1734) that there might be other galaxies – and even clusters of galaxies – in the universe.

Some will argue that everything that is not “tangible” cannot be real. However this opinion is hard to defend if we read the [article](#) of Pim van Lommel et al. in The lancet, volume 358, Issue 9298, P2039-2045, December 15, 2001 (*Near-death experience in survivors of cardiac arrest: a*

prospective study in the Netherlands). Near dead experiences are “out of the body” experiences during physical trauma, resulting in cardiac arrest and the absence of *measurable* brain activity.

Recently I discovered YouTube videos from the [New Thinking Allowed Foundation](#). A number of these videos (7) show interviews between parapsychologist Jeffrey Mishlove and a body that is occupied by 2 consciousnesses, Annika and Tristan. The [latest interview](#) gives a clear picture of what is going on. Be aware that Annika and Tristan don't show the characteristics of a [split brain personality](#) or [dissociative identity disorder](#) (DID). A list of all the NTAF interviews is [here](#). If you watch the interview you can observe the nearly immediately switch between Annika's female extravert expression and Tristan's male introvert expression (inclusive the related voices). Now the question arises if a body with only one consciousness has comparable physical experiences like Annika and Tristan.

In a [previous post](#) I have described the experiment of a person who has to push a button at the moment the display of a computer shows a new picture. The most interesting part of this experiment is – in my opinion – the focus of the person who is involved in this computer executed experiment. The experiment suggests that the focus of the person creates some kind of an “entangled” quantum state with the computer. So it is obvious to ask myself if I can recognise the influence of my focus (concentration) in relation to my physical body. The answer is yes because I can manipulate the focus of my senses (like every human can). If I cut an onion in very small parts during cooking I am focussed on what I am doing because I use a large very sharp knife. Don't expect that I have a vivid conversation at the same moment.

figure 1

However, the description in the interviews about the occupation of the body by Annika and Tristan has a direct relation with the volume of the body. That is imaginable because I cannot type sentences if I focus on my toes. And

even if I don't manage my focus I can experience its change of position inside my body if I met an acquaintance. If I like the person it feels like my heart moves towards the person and if I don't like the person it moves back. Of course it is not my heart (the organ) it is my consciousness as a field that has a volume (a spatial field). Every language has expressions that describe the relation between emotions and parts of the body (she is in love and has butterflies in her stomach, etc.).

figure 2

Most of the surface of the planets that are described by Emanuel Swedenborg are observed by satellites and even landers. So we know a lot about the physical reality on the surfaces of these planets. Even the surface area of [Venus](#) is known with the help of radar equipment from satellite orbits and the planet is visited by Russian landers too ([Venera program](#)). The black and white landscapes in figure 1 show parts of the surface of Venus by a Venera lander. The original pictures are colour pictures although there is no direct sunlight on the surface of Venus (figure 2).

I show these pictures because Emanuel Swedenborg's description of the live of the inhabitants of the planet Venus is different. Swedenborg describes that Venus has 2 types of inhabitants. One half of Venus is inhabited by gentle and peaceful people and on the other side of the planet the inhabitants are wild, cruel and primitive. These societies are mainly agriculture (cattle). It is remarkable that the length of the inhabitants of Venus is much larger than the length of humans (about 3,25 meter).

For the ghosts of the inhabited planets of our solar system the position of a planet in relation to the other planets is more or less fixed. In other words, these persons in the afterlife don't experience the continuous change of position of the planets in their orbits around the Sun. It confirms that consciousness – compositions of displaced vectors (see previous post) – originate from the creation of matter in our universe. It means that a consciousness don't experience a spatial metric, like a consciousness with a material body that is build up by atoms, molecules, etc.

There exist a channelled [description](#) of “the heavens”, inclusive the history of the Milky Way, planet Earth and even a biography of Jesus from Nazareth (Christianity). The title of the book is the [Urantia book](#). Actually, the Urantia book includes 4 related books (I - Central Universe, II – Local Universe, III – the history of the planet Earth, IV – the live of Jesus). I haven’t read part IV (I am not religious). Part I and II maybe only 1 or 2 times. But part III about the history of the planet Earth is really interesting so that is the book I have read a couple of times.

The Urantia book describes the existence of different types of non-material entities and even the existence of “half material” beings (I suppose that these beings represent some type of matter – energy concentrations – without rest mass). The Urantia book doesn’t describe the existence of animal entities and plant entities (although humans are animals too). Nevertheless in human culture there exists a history of vague entities that exist in the natural biosphere, like gnomes and elves. So the afterlife is not limited to humans.

Therefore it is reasonable to expect that displaced vectors reflect the existence and spatial distribution of the rest mass in our universe, inclusive plants and animals. A “conclusion” that is in line with the opinion of the [animal communicator](#) Miranda Alcott (YouTube video [Animals and the afterlife](#)).

Conclusion

It is difficult to conclude that daily reality is limited to the “tangible” part of relational reality. An awkward point of view because in daily live we experience that time has not always a fixed metric – the constant of quantum time (t_q) – and the emotions in our body don’t always rhyme with our concept of space. Therefore it is reasonable to link the displaced vector configurations in quantised space with the [theory of forms](#) of [Plato](#), inclusive live forms.

16 Awareness

The previous post shows the difficulties to describe relational reality with the help of the limited concept of the “tangible” reality of the material world if the subject is related to the awareness of the human consciousness. So if we try to understand the part of relational reality that dominate consciousness (“live itself”) we have to search for useable (math) concepts. At least we can give it a try.

The model of quantised space clarifies the general properties that physics has discovered with the help of experiments (the scientific method). The model explains the existence of the 2 universal conservation laws (energy and momentum), the universal constants (h and c) and some of the universal principles (non-locality and the uncertainty relation). The model also envelopes the general concept of quantum field theory (QFT), inclusive quantum gravity as an emergent vector field. But it also explains the origin of probability and even the non-Doppler red shift of the light of distant galaxies. Unfortunately these are clarifications that are not really helpful to understand “live itself”.

The model of quantised space is a mathematical model. That is why the model shows that the 1 : 1 relation between the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field in the primordial universe changed at the moment that rest mass emerged. The latter means that local concentrations of energy have forced scalars of the Higgs field to decrease their radius. The result is a further increase of the local concentration of energy what is known as rest mass carrying particles.

figure 1

However, decreased scalars interrupt the mediation of vectors by the flat Higgs field (vacuum space). But all the vectors in the universe are conserved (law of conservation of momentum). The consequence is that the interrupted part of a vector will become a displaced vector, like figure 1 shows (2 rest mass carrying particles). These displaced vectors will effect reality in an indirect way, comparable with the use of a side road instead of driving on the direct trajectory.

Unfortunately it is really hard to analyse how this indirect influence will manifest itself because vectors act instantaneous. That means that the position where the displaced vector will effect the energy of the universal electric field – actually the shape of the involved units of quantised space

– is uncertain. Because if my focus is not the rest frame of quantised space, the interpretation of relational reality changes. If the displaced vector is thought to be the frame of reference, the metric of the rest frame becomes meaningless in relation to the position of the displaced vector.

figure 2

Every unit of quantised space without decreased scalar mediates vectors that arrive from adjacent scalars and passed on to other adjacent scalar. See the red scalar in figure 2. That means a distribution of vectors in relation to their direction and a distribution of vectors in relation to their magnitudes. The latter is restricted by the fixed amount of topological deformation of the unit. An amount of topological deformation that is directly related to the synchronisation of the deformation of all the units of quantised space during the constant of quantum time ($1 t_q$). Actually, the synchronisation is responsible for the existence of the quantum of energy, the Planck constant ($\frac{1}{2} h$ for every single unit). The diameter of each scalar in figure 2 is about $0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m.

figure 3

I have drawn a simplified partly transparent unit with the scalar vectors (black) pointing to the positions of the points of contact with the 12 adjacent scalars around (see figure 3). The red and green arrows symbolise the topological deformation of the related faces of the boundary of the unit at a certain moment. In other words, the real shape of the

boundary of the unit is a deformed rhombic dodecahedron because the volume of every unit is invariant. The consequence is that the real surface area of the unit is larger than the surface area of the rhombic dodecahedron.

If during $1 t_q$ a unit deforms in a linear way – one red arrow and at the opposite side one green arrow – the velocity of the change is the speed of light. That makes it easy to understand energy configurations in nature. For example the resultant motion of “free” energy around a concentration of energy. Or the influence of energy density in relation to the properties of electromagnetic waves.

Unfortunately, trying to understand the existence of consciousness with the help of the properties of the corresponding vectors is quite confusing. It seems that there is no “tangible” relation between energy changes (universal electric field) and vectors that are supposed to “create” the awareness of consciousness. The latter means that a consciousness represents a certain volume that has at least slightly different properties than “vector space” (the flat Higgs field) around.

The sum of the *change* of the shape of the 12 faces of a unit during $1 t_q$ can be expressed in terms of surface area and by displaced volume. The latter is easier because the amount of volume of every unit is identical and also invariant ($\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$). In figure 3 the ΔV_{input} are the red arrows, the ΔV_{output} are the green arrows).

The transfer of topological deformation between the units of quantised space is only possible if the total amount of surface area of all the individual units in the universe is conserved. In other words at the hypothetical “start” of the universe every unit of quantised space has a surplus of surface area in comparison with the amount of surface area of a rhombic dodecahedron with exactly the same volume.

Surface area is energy ($E = m c^2$) so it is obvious that the total *surplus* of surface area of all the units in the universe is conserved. The diagram in figure 4 shows the evolution of the asymmetrical energy distribution (the surplus of energy of the mass is equal to the deficit of the free energy in vacuum space).

In other words, if we focus on the total surface area (A) of one unit during $1 t_q$ the equation is different ($\Delta A = \pm 1 h$). The consequence is that during $1 t_q$ the sum of the magnitudes of the vectors corresponds with the change of the surface area of the unit. But the unit has 12 adjacent units.

In other words, all the units of quantised space are forced to “individually” change their surface area with $1 h$ (input + output deformation). Now we can focus on the distribution of the change of surface area of the unit in relation to the change of the magnitudes of the vectors (\mathbf{v}). That means $\Delta v = (\text{maps}) h$.

figure 4

The schematic diagram in figure 5 shows the propagation of an electromagnetic wave in vacuum space. The wave form of the electric field (E) and the magnetic field (B) represent the spatial evolution in the x -direction of the influence of $1 h$ in relation to the electric and magnetic field around. That means that the transfer of $1 h$ by the electromagnetic wave is absorbed by the involved units around and then reversed, etc. Actually the waveform is the distribution of the vector and surface area (energy) of the Planck constant on the units around and the following reaction of the units around.

figure 5

The consequence is that every unit in the x -direction of the electromagnetic wave represents the evolving waveform during $1 t_q$. That means that the duration of the waveform in figure 5 is about $20 t_q$. So figure 5 shows the relevance of the synchronisation of all the changes of the units of quantised space, because without the synchronisation there is no waveform.

Figure 1 shows 2 rest mass carrying particles, the resultant vectors (red) around and the corresponding deformation of the electric field around the particles (concentric circles). Both particles interrupt vectors of the other particle. Vectors that are attached to the decreased scalar of the rest mass carrying particle.

We can observe the asymmetry with the help of experiments. Figure 6 shows the well known [double slit experiment](#). If the slits are very small and close to each other in relation to the wave length of the electromagnetic wave the correspondence between the changes of the universal electric field and the vectors of the magnetic field get out of sync. The screen at the right shows the divergence.

figure 6

In other words, the difference between the velocity of the change of the shape of the units ($c t_q$) and the duration of the change of the corresponding vectors (instantaneous) results in local asymmetries of the correspondence. However, it also shows that the correspondence will “shape” the asymmetry. It is not reasonable to expect that a local surplus or deficit of related vectors will act as an independent phenomenon. The asymmetry is limited by the law of conservation of momentum and the principle of non-locality.

Conclusion

If the focus is on the change of energy we can visualise the change like the change is more or less an isolated occurrence (phenomenological point of view). Because the amount of change is a constant (h), the propagation is a constant (c) and the duration is a constant (t_q). Although the related vectors reflect the change of energy (h), the influence of the vectors has not a clear position in relation to the structure of the units of quantised space. We cannot use the phenomenological point of view to visualise the changes within “vector space” because vectors non-local.

There is a continuous increase of matter in our universe. Therefore the amount of asymmetry of the correspondence

between the universal electric field and the vectors of the magnetic field will not vanish. As long there is matter there will be local consciousness and the awareness of consciousness too.

17 Determinism & probability

The concept of determinism is not really popular. That is understandable because it seems to undermine our efforts to make things better in our live and in our society. No matter what meaning the individual person prefer to “making things better”. However, determinism is not that superficial, the concept is at the core of our universe.

The previous post was about the asymmetrical part of the correspondence between the universal electric field and the vectors of the magnetic field. The terms originate from classic physics but in quantum field theory these terms represent fields at the smallest scale size of reality, inclusive the universal scalar field (Higgs field).

It is obvious to state that the concept of [determinism](#) represents a basic property of relational reality. Actually determinism seems to be more foundational than consciousness. Because if the changes of our universe are deterministic the “principle” envelopes the whole evolution of the universe. So if we think about the manifestation of determinism, what does it represent?

It is for sure that determinism must be a concept that points to an aspect of the law of conservation of energy and the law of conservation of vectors. Because both conservation laws represent the conservation of momentum. Energy is the variable property of the universal electric field and the vectors of the magnetic field correspond with these variances. The universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field are responsible for all the dynamics in the universe.^[1]

One of the arguments to reject determinism is the existence of [probability](#) and its significance in quantum mechanics and quantum theory in general. Because in QM local energy densities are thought to be determined by the probability of the local amplitudes of the electromagnetic field. Unfortunately, [probability theory](#) has no proper mathematical foundation, only axioms (and rules). So rejecting determinism because of the significance of probability in quantum theory is not really convincing. Especially be-

cause the 2 universal conservation laws envelope the electromagnetic field. Therefore universal conservation in relation to the universe means the existence of non-locality and determinism.

If the outcome of every redistribution of energy and its corresponding vectors within the volume of the universe is zero there is no “room” for some kind of uncertainty. In the model of quantized space the redistribution of energy – actually the redistribution of the topological deformation of the shapes of the units of the structure of quantized space – is done by the scalar mechanism of every unit. It manifests itself by the continuous transformation of the shape of every unit of the structure.

The volume of every unit is invariant. So I can express the transformation of the shape of a unit with the help of the amount of transferred volume within the boundary of the unit during the constant of quantum time ($1 t_q$). An amount of volume in relation to the joint surface area with the (12) adjacent units around. So I can express the transfer of volume within the boundary of the unit with the help of a simple equation:

$$\sum \Delta V_1 + \Delta V_2 + \Delta V_3 + \Delta V_4 + \dots + \Delta V_{12} = 0$$

The equation is the sum (Σ) of the transformation in every part of the boundary of the unit. That means that some joint faces will expand their surface area – because of the accumulation of more volume – and other joint faces will shrink their surface area because the whole volume of the unit is invariant. The consequence is that we have to choose which type of volume transfer is positive or negative. In other words, the sum (Σ) unites all the volume transfer to and from the joint faces during $1 t_q$. In line with the invariance of the volume of the unit ($\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$).

figure 1

If we throw [dices](#) the numbers on each side of the dice don't change, so these numbers are invariant. Like the

transferred volume inside every unit of quantized space is invariant. The variance of a dice is limited to the numbers 1 through 6, but the variance of the transferred volume of a unit is perhaps even infinite. However the shape of every unit is reflected by the joint faces of the adjacent units. The consequence is that every unit shows the distribution of its internal volume transfer. Most of the time the shape of the unit reflects nearly the average shape of the units around. That means the amount of asymmetry of the shapes of the units (a symmetrical shape is impossible). But sometimes the shape of the unit is less asymmetrical or more asymmetrical. In other words the unit shows an asymmetrical shape distribution.

Conclusion

Our universe is totally deterministic, there cannot be any doubt. So every human thought, every human emotion and every human action is determined. And it doesn't matter if our consciousness is attached to a material body or not.

Maybe some will become angry about this *impingement* of the universe on our "free will" and self-esteem in relation to others. But we cannot hack the system because we are not the system itself, we are manifestations of relational reality.

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